

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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IDENTIFYING THE MYTHS, BARRIERS, AND FACILITATORS OF
SEXUAL ASSAULT REPORTING

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Sexual assault has existed for thousands of years. Social consequences of not reporting include no justice for victims and allowing perpetrators to reoffend. Yet less than 36% of victims report their sexual assaults to law enforcement.

The project's aim was to create awareness of the myths, barriers, and facilitators of sexual assault reporting to law enforcement. An educational tool, *Sexual Assault Reporting: Guide for First Responders*, was created, validated by an expert panel, and then tested with law enforcement officers for effect on rape myth acceptance. Phase one involved a pretest with demographic, personal, and work-related questions and the 22-item Updated Illinois Rape Myth Acceptance Scale (IRMA). Phase two involved an educational training with the brochure and a posttest, using a modified version of the Updated IRMA to evaluate the effectiveness of the training and brochure.

Despite overall average Updated IRMA score increase (less rape myth acceptance at posttest), MANOVA analysis revealed no significant difference in mean scores (pre to posttest) for 19 officers who took both. Two items specific to drinking and victim appearance, extremely common rape myth stereotypes, showed average increased scores of almost 1, indicating more rejection of these rape myths at post-test.

Overall, in this small evaluation of the pamphlet, results were encouraging and demonstrated that the educational training using the brochure, *Sexual Assault Reporting: Guide for First Responders*, may lead to increased rape myth rejection. Further evaluations with larger samples, especially of wider geographic nature, are warranted.

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BACKGROUND

Rape is sexual intercourse with an individual who does not and/or cannot legally give consent (e.g., a person who was forced or coerced, a person under the influence of drugs and/or alcohol, an unconscious person, a person asleep, a person below the age of consent, or a mentally and/or physically disabled person). The Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI) broadened its definition of forcible rape from penetration with a penis into the vagina to include forced anal and oral penetration, penetration by a foreign object or other parts of the body, rape of a woman by a woman, and a rape of a man (Peterson, 2013). This change was a result of federal agencies and national victim advocacy organizations advocating for the definition of rape to be broadened to include these additional acts (Peterson, 2013).

The word *rape* originated from the Latin word *rapere*, which implies to carry away, steal, or seize. Rape as a phenomenon has existed for thousands of years, dating back to the early ages when women were viewed as property. For example, the Old Testament described laws regarding rape and the consequences to both the offender and victim. In the book of Deuteronomy (22:23-29 King James Version), it was written that if a married woman was raped in town, it was an automatic death sentence for both the woman and the offender. The rationale for this punishment centered on the notion that if the woman would have cried out for help, someone would have heard her. In this situation, the woman would be judged a guilty party. Biblical verses also noted that if a married woman was raped in the country, she would not die because there was no one to help her and only the offender would be sentenced to death (Deuteronomy 22:23-29). In contrast to the previous situation, the woman is judged innocent because of location.

Furthermore, if a woman was raped and was a virgin and not pledged to another man, the rapist would give the father of the virgin 50 pieces of silver. The woman would then be forced to marry her rapist with no chance of divorce (Deuteronomy 22:23-29).

In ancient laws, punishment hinged on three elements—the victim's and/or rapist's social status, how society judged the victim, and the physical location of the rape. Many of these factors still hold true today. Society continues to make judgments about the guilt or innocence of females who have been raped depending on their marital status, what the woman was wearing, and where the assault took place.

National and local state data reveal significant findings related to sexual assault crimes. The National Crime Victimization Survey (NCVS) is a random survey conducted annually by the U.S. Census Bureau for the U.S. Department of Justice (2013) and is considered one of the largest databases on criminal victimization, aside from the crime reports that law enforcement agencies send to the FBI Uniform Crime Reporting Program. NCVS data revealed that approximately 270,000 females, 12 years and older, were sexually assaulted in 2010 (U.S. Department of Justice, 2013). Data reported in 2010 by the California Department of Justice (2011) documented 7,408 forcible rapes and 917 attempted rapes per 100,000 females.

NCVS data collected from 2005 to 2010 revealed 38% of sexual violent acts were committed by an acquaintance or friend, 34% by an intimate partner (a former or current spouse, girlfriend, or boyfriend), and 6% by a family member or a relative. Rape by strangers constituted 22% of all sexual violence; this number did not significantly change from 1994 to 2010 (U.S. Department of Justice, 2013). Data from 2005 to 2010 demonstrated that in 11% of sexual assault cases the offender was reported to be armed

with a gun, knife, or other weapon. Also, during this same time period, approximately 58% of female victims were physically injured during the assault (e.g., bruising, cuts, broken bones, internal injuries, gunshot wounds, or rape injuries). This percentage remained unchanged from statistics gathered during the timeframe of 1994 to 1998 and from 2005 to 2010. However, there was an increase in medical treatment sought for injuries related to sexual assaults, with 26% of victims seeking medical assistance during the years from 1994 to 1998 in contrast to 35% of victims seeking care during the timeframe of 2005 to 2010 (U.S. Department of Justice, 2013).

The Bureau of Justice Statistics (2000) reported that 67% of sexual assault victims are under 18 years of age, 34% are under 12, and 14% are under 6 years of age. NCVS data reported that nine of every 10 rape victims are female, and one in 10 is male (U.S. Department of Justice, 2013). Tjaden and Thoennes (2000) reported that one out of six American women has been a victim of attempted or completed rape in her lifetime (2.8% attempted and 14.8% completed), which equates to 17.7 million American women who have been victims of an attempted or a completed rape in their lifetime. Reports have shown that 3% or one in 33 American men has experienced an attempted or completed rape in their lifetime, which equates to 2.78 million men having been victims of sexual assault or rape (Tjaden & Thoennes, 2000).

Problem Statement

The ramifications of sexual assault are ongoing for victims even years after the event. They are three times more likely to be affected by depression, six times more likely to suffer from posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD), 13 times more likely to abuse alcohol, 26 times more likely to abuse drugs, and four times more likely to consider

suicide (Rape Abuse and Incest National Network [RAINN], 2009). All of these dire statistics illustrate the need of these victims for emotional support at the time of the incident and afterwards.

From 1995 to 2005, the incidence of sexual violence against women, 12 years and older, decreased by 64% from 5.0 per 1,000 females to 1.8 and has remained unchanged through 2010 (U.S. Department of Justice, 2013). Although any decrease in the number of assaults is welcomed, unfortunately, this reduction does not negate the fact that sexual violence still occurs in epidemic proportions in the United States. The negative consequences of sexual assault for victims and our society are devastating. Notably, President Barack Obama addressed the issue of sexual assault as an epidemic on college campuses and launched an initiative to combat this crime (Gillum, 2014). He appointed members to a taskforce and gave them 90 days to identify solutions to prevent sexual assault on campuses, increase public awareness on college campuses, and hold these colleges accountable if they do not handle the problem (Gillum, 2014).

NCVS sexual assault data revealed interesting findings. During the period from 2005 to 2010, 36% of sexual assault victims reported this crime to law enforcement. Of the 36%, approximately 64% of these victims reported the incident to law enforcement, 10% were reported by a member of the household, 14% were reported by an official other than the police, 10% were reported by someone else, 1% of the time the police were at the crime scene, and 1% were reported by some other means. Law enforcement responded to approximately 84% of the cases reported by victims (U.S. Department of Justice, 2013).

Between 2005 and 2010, law enforcement took a police statement in 86% of reported cases to which they responded, and 48% of the time they questioned additional witnesses or conducted a search for the offender. However, the percentage of reported cases of sexual assaults that resulted in an arrest either at the scene or at follow-up was 47% during the 5-year period from 1994 to 1998 and decreased to 31% from 2005 to 2010 (U.S. Department of Justice, 2013).

The relationship of the assailant to the victim and the location where the sexual assault occurred vary. Almost two thirds of sexual assaults are committed by someone the victim knows. Four out of 10 rapes occur in the victim's home; two out of 10 rapes take place at the home of a friend, relative, or neighbor; and one in 12 occurs in a parking garage (U.S. Department of Justice, 2013). These facts support that rapists are not lurking behind the bushes or in the alleys as is often portrayed by the media on television and in the movies. The rapist can be a friend, neighbor, acquaintance, relative, boyfriend, or husband. When the victim knows the perpetrator, the situation becomes much more complicated and typically the dilemma of not reporting begins.

From 2005 to 2010, NCVS data reported that 36 out of every 100 rapes were reported to law enforcement; 19 will lead to an arrest (U.S. Department of Justice, 2013). During this same time period, the data demonstrated that 64 sexual assaults out of 100 were not reported to law enforcement. The annual average percentage of arrests with both reported and nonreported sexual assaults to law enforcement is 12% (U.S. Department of Justice, 2013). The National Center for Policy Analysis documented that 8% of reported cases are prosecuted (Reynolds, 1999) and, according to the U.S. Department of Justice (2010), 4% lead to a felony conviction. Clearly, the reporting (36%) and conviction rates

(4%) are extremely low. It is evident that in order for more prosecution to take place, victims of sexual assault must disclose this heinous crime to law enforcement. Thus, it is imperative that victims come forward to allow for the proper collection and handling of evidence as this directly impacts the legal implications for prosecution and conviction of the offender (Stermac, Dunlap, & Bainbridge, 2005).

When a violent crime such as rape is not reported, the perpetrator can keep reoffending, which negatively affects more lives, as documented in multiple research surveys. Lisak and Miller (2002) surveyed 1,882 men using the Sexual Experiences Survey. The Sexual Experiences Survey is considered the most extensive and informative survey used to collect and analyze data about adult sexual aggression. Findings by Lisak and Miller revealed that 120 men self-reported having raped another for a total of 1,225 incidents of interpersonal violence. Of these 120 men, over 80% raped women who were under the influence of drugs and/or alcohol; 9.2% used force or threats to coerce sex; 10% used force or threats for oral sex; and 76 of the 120 men committed repeat rapes, averaging 5.8 rapes per individual (Lisak & Miller, 2002). This study reaffirmed that sexual offenders do not rape just once; rapists are typically repeat offenders.

Needs Assessment

Clearly, victims of sexual abuse (rape) suffer many negative ramifications beyond the actual event and whether or not the assault is reported. The literature demonstrated that many victims of sexual assault are afraid to report (Ellis, 2002; Sable, Danis, Mauzy, & Gallagher, 2006). They are reluctant to describe what occurred and opt to stay silent. Because victims may be fearful of physical retaliation by the perpetrator, many believe that nondisclosure is a means of protecting themselves and/or their family. Nevertheless,

not reporting and staying silent are often detrimental to their physical and/or emotional health as they typically suffer alone while the perpetrator suffers no consequence and often will rape again (Ellis, 2002; Sable et al., 2006).

Victims of sexual assault who remain silent cannot receive the physical and emotional care they need to heal. Consequently, law enforcement cannot protect others from such violent crimes when sexual assault is not reported. With approximately 64% of sexual assaults unreported (U.S. Department of Justice, 2013), law enforcement officers, first responders, and health professionals must work to help victims overcome their reluctance to reporting sexual crimes and encourage them to provide full and accurate disclosure of the event. Furthermore, those who work with sexual assault victims need to be well-versed in therapeutic interviewing and knowledgeable about facilitators and barriers (i.e., myths associated with sexual assault) to disclosing sexual assault. Thus, educational resources and a targeted community of interest program are needed to improve the reporting of sexual assault.

Conceptual Framework

To achieve the goal of creating an educational brochure for the multidisciplinary team members who work with victims of sexual assault, two theoretical models were chosen to provide the foundation for this project (see Figure 1). The two theoretical models included Lynch's forensic nursing integrated practice model, a collaborative approach to nursing practice (Lynch & Duval, 2011), and Knowles' adult learning principles, a model for adult education (Knowles, 1980).

Figure 1. Conceptual framework for forensic educational brochure.

Virginia Lynch is known internationally as the pioneer of forensic nursing in the United States. Her 1986 graduate research project was titled, “Clinical Forensic Nursing: A Descriptive Study in Role Development,” in which she advocated using a multidisciplinary team approach with trauma victims and addressed the importance of preserving criminal evidence (Lynch & Duval, 2011). Lynch’s forensic integrated practice model (see Figure 2) was the first, and remains the only, nursing practice model that describes and utilizes forensic concepts salient to nursing. Because Lynch’s forensic nursing integrated practice model speaks directly to both nursing and forensic concepts, this model provided the framework, structure for, and emphasis for the content included in the educational tool that was used in this project with law enforcement officers.

Figure 2. Lynch’s forensic nursing integrated practice model. From V. A. Lynch & J. B. Duval, 2014, *Forensic Nursing Science* (2nd ed.), p. 13. Reprinted with permission; see Appendices A and B.

In 1990, Virginia Lynch developed a theoretical framework for forensic nursing. Lynch's model acknowledges that forensic nursing draws knowledge from nursing science, criminal justice, and forensic science. Her integrated practice model has provided the structure for many forensic nursing programs and has shaped their policies and educational training and curricular content throughout the United States and internationally (Lynch & Duval, 2011). This model proposes a complementary partnership for nursing professionals with respect to their role in the multidisciplinary team approach to patient care for assault victims (Lynch & Duval, 2011).

Lynch's model emphasizes the need to provide traditional nursing interventions with forensic knowledge and skills (Lynch & Duval, 2011). The multidisciplinary approach assists with crisis care and the interactions between health care professionals, other disciplines, traumatized victims, family members, and the offenders. The central theme of Lynch's forensic nursing model is the incorporation of theories from social, legal, and nursing sciences to provide mutual benefits to the patient, society, health care institution, law, and human behavior (Lynch & Duval, 2011).

The Lynch model is presented as Figure 2. The outer circles represent the interacting environments of society and education. The three main constructs—fields of expertise, health care system, and societal impact—are located at the tips of the triangle. At the top of the triangle are three interlocking circles under the fields of expertise. These three circles depict the areas from which forensic nursing draws its knowledge. These interlocking circles pictorially symbolize the vital multidisciplinary communication, coordination, and cooperation that need to exist among the different disciplines involved in the care of the sexual assault victim. The three circles at the bottom left symbolize the

dynamics that dictate the role performance of the forensic nurse. The bottom three circles symbolize the disciplines' emerging relationships with forensic nursing and the health care facilities as they relate to victims and their significant others (Lynch & Duval, 2011).

The symbol that is centrally located in the triangle represents forensic science having the scales of justice interlaced with the medical caduceus. The eternal flame represents enlightenment with this new field of nursing. The science of forensic nursing and its humanitarian outlook are the foundations for discovering new solutions to difficulties that necessitate a unique multidisciplinary team approach (Lynch & Duval, 2011). Therefore, by utilizing Lynch's integrated practice model in the creation and dissemination of the project's brochure, *Sexual Assault Reporting: Guide for First Responders*, the researcher is effectively combining science, law, forensic medicine, and the biopsychosocial spiritual being of nursing to provide an educational tool to overcome one of the many barriers (i.e., sexual assault myths) associated with reluctance to report a sexual assault.

Aside from the contents of this educational tool, this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) student is concerned about how this brochure could best achieve its goal. The purpose of this project was twofold. The first purpose was to explore the views of police officers about victims of sexual assault and issues surrounding the reporting of these crimes. A secondary aim of the project was to evaluate the effectiveness of a brochure and roll-call educational session repeated multiple times for different groups of officers. The goal of the session was to increase awareness of factors that influence reporting of sexual assault by victims of this crime. Lastly, to increase acceptance and use of the

brochure by first responders, the Knowles' adult learning principles was used in the dissemination process.

Malcolm Knowles is known internationally as one of the leading authorities on adult learning principles (Knowles, Holton, & Swanson, 1998). His work explains the unique aspects of adult learning and provides vast insight into strategies for teaching adults. Because this doctoral student used her educational brochure in conducting multiple training sessions with law enforcement officers, the participants in this project were adult learners. Thus, Knowles' learning principles were used for this project that involved adults with varied educational backgrounds. The brochure training session was conducted as part of roll-call briefings with law enforcement and included multiple presentations covering the brochure material. Therefore, to maximize learning opportunities, the Knowles' principles and guidelines were used during the educational sessions.

The theoretical formulation of art and science in helping adults learn was first described as andragogy in the early 1960s European literature (Kaufman, 2003). At a later time, Knowles (1980) introduced the term *andragogy* to his North America readership and added five essential principles that characterized adult learners (see Figure 3). Knowles theorized that adults learn most effectively if five important principles are considered.

First, as people age, their self-concept goes from being dependent to being independent and self-directed (Knowles, 1980). In order to encourage and develop these traits in learners, Knowles (1980) believed that opportunities need to exist for learners to

Figure 3. Knowles' adult learning principles.

acquire and practice skills, raise inquiries by asking questions, recognize their own knowledge and skill differences, and reflect on their learning outcomes.

The second principle Knowles (1980) believed was that adult learners define their identity through their life experiences. As individuals develop, they accumulate a reservoir of experiences that becomes an expanding resource for learning. One of the implications for practice that Knowles recommended is *unfreezing*, a phenomenon when adult learners are able to look at themselves as being more objective and open minded. This phenomenon occurs when adults can free their minds from preconceptions, such as the myths associated with rape.

Knowles' (1980) third principle is readiness to learn. As individuals age, their readiness to learn becomes increasingly oriented to the developmental task of their social

roles. For example, Knowles thought that adult learners only devote the time and energy to learn something if they felt the information would help them with tasks or to deal with problems in their real life environment.

Knowles' (1980) fourth principle is an orientation to learning. As adults mature, their orientation to learning changes from subject-centeredness to one of problem-centeredness or performance-centeredness. Time perspective can then shift from one of postponed application of knowledge to immediate application. This fourth principle deals with how adult learners are more inspired to learn because of pressures in dealing with current life situations. The adult attends an educational activity due to a performance-centered or a problem-centered frame of mind.

Finally, the fifth principle proposed by Knowles (1980) is the motivation to learn. With advancing age, an individual's motivation to learn is internalized. Knowles provides guidance about how to utilize his principles by thoroughly explaining, encouraging, recognizing, and offering positive reinforcement.

In summary, two theoretical models were utilized to provide the underpinnings of this project—Lynch's forensic nursing integrated practice model and Knowles' adult learning principles. Lynch's forensic nursing integrated practice model addresses both nursing and forensic concepts. Lynch's model recognizes that forensic nursing draws wisdom from nursing science in addition to criminal justice and forensic science. Lynch's integrated model addresses the unique role of the forensic nurse as a key member of the multidisciplinary team responsible for the care of sexual assault victims (Lynch & Duval, 2011). Thus, it provided a solid framework from which to design this project. A letter requesting permission to replicate Lynch's model for this project and a

letter of approval from Elsevier Publishers are included in Appendices A and B, respectively.

Malcolm Knowles' adult learning principles provide knowledge related to best educational practices as well as practical strategies for teaching the adult population. Because the objective of this project was to conduct multiple training sessions for one law enforcement agency using the author's brochure, *Sexual Assault Reporting: Guide for First Responders*, Knowles' principles of self-concept, the role of experience, readiness to learn, orientation to learning, and motivation were applicable (Knowles, 1980). Knowles' principles and guidelines were utilized in planning the training developed for this project in order to maximize learning opportunities. Therefore, this DNP student used the Lynch's forensic nursing integrated practice model and Knowles' adult learning principles to guide her in developing the brochure to ensure that adult learners, such as law enforcement officers, would find the educational tool (the project's brochure) and training session beneficial in their work with victims of sexual assault.

Purpose

The purpose of this doctoral project was twofold. The first goal was to explore the views of police officers in one urban setting about victims of sexual assault and issues surrounding the reporting of these crimes. The second goal was to evaluate the effectiveness of a brochure and roll-call educational session to increase awareness of factors that influence reporting of sexual assault by victims of this crime.

In order to accomplish the first goal, the Updated Illinois Rape Myth Acceptance Scale was used to assess preintervention perceptions of law enforcement officers. To accomplish the second goal, an educational resource, *Sexual Assault Reporting: Guide*

for First Responders, was created as a resource tool for law enforcement officers involved in interviewing sexual assault victims. This educational resource was developed for officers to increase their awareness of myths, barriers, and facilitators related to reporting sexual assault and to identify evidenced-based strategies that promote therapeutic interviewing of victims. A script was developed for the training sessions (the intervention to acquaint officers with the brochure). To measure the effectiveness of the brochure and training session, a posttest was used (i.e., the Updated Illinois Rape Myth Acceptance Scale was modified to use as the posttest component for this project).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

To establish a framework for this project, an extensive review of literature on sexual assault was conducted. Thus, for this project, the review of literature focused on six areas. The first part of this review discusses research that identified myths, barriers, and facilitators of sexual assault reporting, including resources for both law enforcement and victims. This next section describes the anatomy of the limbic system and research related to the concept of tonic immobility (TI). The phenomenon of TI is not well understood among first responders and victims and was judged to be important to include as a topic covered in this review of literature. All six topics were addressed in the brochure in order for the educational sessions for police officers to be comprehensive and effective.

Literature Search Strategy

Myths, Barriers, and Facilitators

Initially, myths, barriers, and facilitators were examined. The literature search strategy consisted of peer-reviewed articles from journals in the fields of nursing, psychology, sociology, women's studies, and criminal justice. The search included utilization of the California State University, Fullerton, online library. Search terms included *sexual assault and barriers*, *sexual assault and stereotypes*, *sexual assault victims*, *barriers of reporting sexual assault*, *sexual assault and men*, *sexual assault and women*, *sexual assault and facilitators*, *increase in sexual assault reporting*, *reporting sexual assault*, *police and sexual assault victims*, and *police issues in dealing with sexual assault*. The search resulted in over 700 titles of articles and, of these, 44 abstracts were read and 22 sources were included in this project.

Article selection criteria for inclusion in the literature review were as follows: (a) articles written in English, (b) women sexual assault victims, (c) male sexual assault victims, and (d) articles written from 2001 to 2014 that were pertinent to the topic under investigation. The exclusion criteria included articles written about child sexual assault and domestic violence. Searching the research literature using the phrase *sexual assault and barriers* yielded 47 publications from the CINAHL database and 58 from the PubMed database. Of these publications, eight articles were applicable to the topic and were included.

The combination term *sexual assault and stereotypes* was used to search the CINAHL database and resulted in seven additional publications. However, only one article was applicable and included as part of the literature reviewed for this project. The CINAHL database also identified 124 publications using the search terms *sexual assault victims*, with one article that met project criteria. Additional terms used in database exploration included *barriers of reporting sexual assault*, *sexual assault and facilitators*, *sexual assault and men*, and *sexual assault and women*. The results of the *barriers of reporting sexual assault* search revealed three publications; however, these articles were duplicates from other searches. The search terms *sexual assault and men* revealed 38 publications, with one article judged relevant. Finally, using the terms *sexual assault and women* uncovered 57 publications, with two pertinent articles retrieved for the literature review. The researcher was able to identify one additional article that was relevant to this theme through reference mining.

PubMed was also searched for relevant articles. The combination term *increase in sexual assault reporting* was explored to identify facilitators. Of the 23 publications

discovered, only one was deemed useful. Searching using *reporting sexual assault* generated 249 publications, with seven selected; however, five of the seven were duplicate articles. Therefore, only two were included in the literature review. The Criminal Justice database was also searched to retrieve additional articles. The terms *police and sexual assault victims* generated 180 publications, with four judged relevant. Similarly, inputting *police issues in dealing with sexual assault* identified two publications; one was appropriate for this project. Having completed a comprehensive search using the CINAHL, PubMed, and Criminal Justice databases, a total of 22 publications were selected for the literature review that then served to guide the development of the project's educational tool and the rape myth data collection study involving law enforcement. Eighteen of these publications were peer reviewed articles.

Limbic System

The search also included a review of literature on the limbic system (e.g., fight, flight, and freeze response—also known as TI) and how these physiological responses are manifested in sexual assault victims due to trauma. The literature search strategy involved seeking out peer-reviewed articles from journals in psychology, anxiety disorders, behavior research and therapy, and interpersonal violence. The search included utilization of the California State University, Fullerton, online library and Google search. Search terms included *tonic immobility and sexual assault*, *tonic immobility and childhood sexual assault*, *limbic system and sexual assault*, and *physiological responses and sexual assault*. Over 6,160 titled articles were found; however, of these, four useable articles were read and three sources were included in the project.

Rape Myths

The review of literature demonstrated that there are many barriers to sexual assault reporting. One major barrier is rape myth acceptance attitudes. Acceptance of rape myths appears to be a leading barrier associated with the lack of reporting sexual assault. Research in the United States and United Kingdom has shown that females endorse fewer rape myths than males (Rich & Seffrin, 2012). A study conducted by Talbot, Neill, and Rankin (2010) revealed significant differences between men and women in their rape accepting attitudes. Talbot et al. assessed the rape accepting attitudes of 1,602 undergraduate university students; 62% were females and 38% were males. The men were more traditional in gender beliefs, which correlated with an increase in rape myth acceptance. In contrast, the women in this study were less accepting of rape myths. A meta-analysis conducted by E. Suarez and Gadalla (2010) also showed that men exhibited a significantly higher agreement with rape myth acceptance than women. These findings were strongly associated with a male mindset and actions that were hostile toward women, hence supporting the feminist argument that sexism enables rape myth acceptance (E. Suarez & Gadalla, 2010).

The review of literature conducted for this project identified multiple rape myths that are presented in Tables 1 and 2. These rape myths mostly transfer culpability for the rape from the criminal to the victim. This transference explains the sociocultural context of adverse reaction to taking legal action, which is an important influence that prevents victims from reporting (E. Suarez & Gadalla, 2010). Rape myths shape how perpetrators view their victims; how victims view themselves; how other people view the perpetrator

Table 1

Rape Myths from the Updated Illinois Rape Myth Acceptance Scale

Myth

-
1. If a girl is raped while she is drunk, she is at least somewhat responsible for letting things get out of hand.
 2. When girls go to parties wearing slutty clothes, they are asking for trouble.
 3. If a girl goes to a room alone with a guy at a party, it is her own fault if she is raped.
 4. If a girl acts like a slut, eventually she is going to get into trouble.
 5. When girls get raped, it's often because the way they said "no" was unclear.
 6. If a girl initiates kissing or hooking up, she should not be surprised if a guy assumes she wants to have sex.
 7. When guys rape, it is usually because of their strong desire for sex.
 8. Guys don't usually intend to force sex on a girl, but sometimes they get too sexually carried away.
 9. Rape happens when a guy's sex drive goes out of control.
 10. If a guy is drunk, he might rape someone unintentionally.
 11. It shouldn't be considered rape if a guy is drunk and didn't realize what he was doing.
 12. If both people are drunk, it can't be rape.
 13. If a girl doesn't physically resist sex-even if protesting verbally-it can't be considered rape.
 14. If a girl doesn't physically fight back, you can't really say it was rape.
 15. A rape probably doesn't happen if a girl doesn't have any bruises or marks.
 16. If the accused "rapist" doesn't have a weapon, you really can't call it rape.
 17. If a girl doesn't say "no" she can't claim rape.
 18. A lot of times, girls who say they were raped agreed to have sex and then regret it.
 19. Rape accusations are often used as a way of getting back at guys.
 20. A lot of times, girls who say they were raped often led the guy on and then had regrets.
 21. A lot of times, girls who claim they were raped have emotional problems.
 22. Girls who are caught cheating on their boyfriends sometimes claim it was rape.
-

Note. From McMahon and Farmer (2011) and Payne, Lonsway, and Fitzgerald (1999).

Table 2

Male Sexual Assault Myths

Myth

1. Boys can't be sexually used or abused, and if one is, he can never be a "real man."
2. If a boy experienced sexual arousal during abuse, and/or if he wanted and/or enjoyed it, and/or if he ever did partly want the sexual experiences, then it was his fault.
3. Sexual abuse is less harmful to boys than girls.
4. Most men who sexually abuse boys are gay.
5. Boys abused by males must have attracted the abuse because they are gay or they become gay as a result.
6. If a female used or abused a boy, he was "Lucky," and if he doesn't feel that way there's something wrong with him.
7. Boys who are sexually abused will go on to abuse others.

Note. From Onein6 (2014).

and victim, including jurors; and how prosecutors and police officers attribute responsibility for the act of rape (Rich & Seffrin, 2012).

Early studies reported that law enforcement officers appeared to endorse more rape myths than other professional groups and the general public (Lonsway & Fitzgerald, 1994). However, recent studies have shown less acceptance of rape myths by law enforcement than what had been their beliefs about rape in the past. This change has been attributed to education and professional experience (Page, 2010). However, there is still a wide range of inconsistency in beliefs about rape among law enforcement officers responding to sexual assault complaints from women; thus, sexual assault victims are still at risk for victimization (Rich & Seffrin, 2012).

Rich and Seffrin (2012) surveyed 429 law enforcement officers to assess their rape myth acceptance. Their data confirmed the researchers' hypothesis that the acceptance of rape myths among law enforcement is a significant predictor of the focus taken when interviewing sexual assault victims. Studies about rape myth acceptance comparing female officers and male officers are scarce. However, Rich and Seffrin conducted a study with female officers and found that the women in their study had a lower average score related to rape myth acceptance than men—that is, they were more rejecting of rape myths. These researchers noted that their findings were consistent with previous studies—two involved a quantitative research design (Brown & King, 1998; Page, 2007) and one was a qualitative study (Schwartz, 2010).

Finding from the aforementioned three studies were consistent with the research findings of Rich and Seffrin (2012) on the acceptance of rape myths and gender. Rich and Seffrin also noted that female officers' rape myth acceptance and interviewing skills as

demonstrated via a questionnaire were significantly more effective than male officers'. These researchers associated this finding with female officers' lower levels of rape myth acceptance (Rich & Seffrin, 2012). Furthermore, they noted that female officers in their study had significantly more sexual assault training than male officers and female officers also reported that they personally knew more sexual assault victims than their male counterparts (Rich & Seffrin, 2012).

Barriers to Reporting Rape

Multiple barriers to reporting sexual assault have been documented in the literature. Please refer to Table 3 for a culmination of these many barriers. A study by Jones, Alexander, Wynn, Rossman, and Dunnuck (2007) identified variables that differentiated female sexual assault victims who reported being assaulted from those who did not report. Their study showed that nonreporting victims were more likely to be employed (69% vs. 54%), had a history of alcohol or drug use (70% vs. 51%), and knew the assailant (70% vs. 88%) than those who reported the crime. Not wanting the offender to go to jail (66% vs. 9%, $p < .001$), knowing the offender (54% vs. 23%, $p < .001$), and concern law enforcement would be insensitive or blame the victim (51% vs. 15%, $p < .001$) were also factors identified by nonreporters that differed significantly from responses of their female counterparts who were willing to report rape (Jones et al., 2007).

Vidal and Petrak (2007) investigated feelings of shame in 25 female sexual assault victims using the 25-item Experience of Shame Scale (ESS) and the 22-item Impact of Events Scale-Revised (IES-R). They compared scores of 25 sexual assault victims with a validation group of 163 undergraduate students in the United Kingdom

Table 3

Barriers to Sexual Assault Reporting

Barrier

-
1. Prolonged time between the assault and forensic exam
 2. Not wanting perpetrator to go to jail
 3. Fear of retaliation
 4. Victims felt law enforcement would be insensitive or blame her or him for assault
 5. Victims felt responsible for the sexual assault
 6. Victims were concern of public exposure
 7. Victims believe it was a personal matter
 8. Victims believe it is not important enough
 9. Victims believe law enforcement could not do anything to help
 10. Victims believe law enforcement would not do anything to help
 11. Victims did not want to get in trouble
 12. Victims did not want to involve law enforcement or the courts
 13. Victims did that think it was serious enough, not a crime
 14. Victims handled it themselves
 15. Financial dependence on the perpetrator
 16. Perpetrator not allowing the sexual assault victim to obtain help
 17. Lack of resources to obtain help (e.g., transportation, childcare, money, and insurance).
-

Note. From Jones, Alexander, Wynn, Rossman, and Dunnuck (2007); Sable et al. (2006); U.S. Department of Justice (2013); and Zinzow and Thompson (2011).

who had also completed the ESS and the IES-R. Their study showed that 14 of the 25 had also been victims of previous sexual assaults (12 of the 14 assaults occurred in childhood), 20 of the 25 knew their offender as an acquaintance or a partner, 20 of the 25 avoided telling others, 13 of the 25 kept it a secret, and 16 of the 25 felt they were to blame. Comparing the ESS scores of the 25 females to the validation sample, the behavioral and body shame scores were significantly higher ($p < .01$) for the 25 females. The IES-R scores also showed that the 25 females had a significantly higher ($p < .01$) score related to avoidance than the validation group. Vidal and Petrak also compared their subjects' score to those who participated in the Creamer, Bell, and Failla (2003) study. The work of Creamer et al. investigated the IES-R scores of Vietnam veterans. The IES-R scores of the 25 women suggested 22 of these women were suffering from traumatic stress as their scores were significantly higher ($p < .05$) than the Vietnam veterans' scores on this same measure.

The Vidal and Petrak (2007) study also investigated the relationship between various types of shame and the experience of the sexual assault. Higher shame scores were related to increases in traumatic stress ($p < .05$). Sexual assault victims who blamed themselves for the sexual assault had higher scores for behavioral shame about their self ($p < .05$) and their body ($p < .01$). Women who had some form of physical consequence from their sexual assaults scored significantly higher with body shame ($p < .05$) compared to women in this study who did not suffer a physical consequence. In addition, women who had a medical exam following the sexual assault had significantly higher body shame scores ($p < .05$) compared to women who had no medical exam. Women who kept the sexual assault a secret showed an increase in shame related to how others

saw them ($p < .01$) and how others perceived them ($p < .05$) compared to those who disclosed. Women also had an increase in shame with themselves ($p < .05$) and their body ($p < .05$) if they knew the suspect as compared to a stranger assault. Lastly, women who experienced multiple sexual assaults scored significantly higher on the following: characterological shame subscale ($p < .05$), body shame ($p < .05$), and concern as to how others thought about them ($p < .05$; Vidal & Petrak, 2007).

Zinzow and Thompson (2011) conducted a study to identify the frequency of sexual assault in college females during their freshman year and barriers to reporting this crime. Of the 719 females surveyed, 127 reported being victims of sexual assault. Of these 127 women, 108 (85%) did not report the sexual assault to law enforcement. Statistically significant differences in reporting barriers were noted between female freshmen who reported or did not report their sexual assault. Barriers included issues of shame and not wanting others involved if victims were physically injured during the sexual assault ($p < .01$), the offender was a relative ($p < .05$), and perceptions of self-blame ($p < .01$). The most common barriers identified in this study are listed in Table 4.

A study by Sable et al. (2006) identified barriers to reporting sexual assault and gender differences in reporting between women and men. This study consisted of 215 college students from a Psychology 1 course; 55% were female and 45% were male. Significant findings for nonreporting were found for both genders. The barriers addressed by women were as follows: fear of retaliation ($p < .001$), financial dependence with offender ($p < .001$), offender not allowing victim to obtain help ($p < .001$), lack of resources to obtain help (e.g., transportation, childcare, money, insurance; $p < .001$), not wanting the offender to be prosecuted ($p < .05$), and cultural or language barriers to

Table 4

Most Common Barriers to Sexual Assault

Barrier
Handled it myself ($n = 76$; 70%)
Not serious enough/not a crime ($n = 73$; 68%)
Didn't want anyone to know ($n = 49$; 45%)
Didn't want police/court involvement ($n = 45$; 43%)
Shame or embarrassment ($n = 44$; 42%)
Didn't want him arrested, jailed, deported, or stressed ($n = 35$; 33%)
Police couldn't do anything ($n = 31$; 30%)
Would be viewed as my fault ($n = 24$; 23%)
Didn't want relationship to end ($n = 13$; 12%)
Reported to someone else ($n = 11$; 11%)
Scared of offender ($n = 9$; 9%)
Wouldn't be believed ($n = 6$; 6%)

Note. Information adapted from Zinzow and Thompson's (2011) study.

obtaining help ($p < .05$). The reasons listed by the men included the following: shame, guilt, and embarrassment ($p < .001$); concerns about confidentiality ($p < .01$); and fear of not being believed ($p < .01$; Sable et al., 2006).

Misconceptions surrounding male sexual assault can lead to underreporting and secondary victimization by law enforcement, emergency staff, medical doctors, nurses, and community health services. Ellis (2002) reported that male sexual assault victims may believe the attack has threatened their masculinity, especially if they are unable to defend themselves and fear they will be viewed as homosexual or not a man. Male victims may also report that they were sexually aroused and had an erection and/or ejaculated. For both homosexual males and heterosexual males who are adolescent victims, these physiological responses create psychological conflicts about their sexuality. Therefore, many male victims only request assistance when they need medical help because of physical and/or psychological trauma (Ellis, 2002). As a result, they are treated poorly and have secondary trauma typically termed as sanctuary trauma or secondary victimization. This phenomenon results from a lack of empathy and understanding from the first responders. Ellis noted that training is needed for first responders. He suggested that those working with male victims must first explore their attitudes about male sexual assault if they are to provide empathetic support to male victims.

Davies and Rogers (2006) conducted a literature review focusing on the perceptions of male sexual assault victims and found that females are victimized more often than men. Male sexual assault, however, is still underreported more often than female sexual assault and is most likely to occur during adolescence and young

adulthood. The reasons both males and females typically do not report sexual assault are their fear of being blamed for the assault and/or not being believed. Davies and Rogers described two types of blame—behavioral blame and characterological blame. Behavioral blame occurs when the victim believes he or she did something to cause the sexual assault (e.g., a behavior), whereas characterological blame occurs when the individual believes the sexual assault had something to do with his or her character. These attitudes greatly influence whether or not victims report sexual assault to law enforcement or seek medical help. Overall, men blame female sexual assault victims more than women blame female sexual assault victims. Similarly, men typically blame male sexual assault victims more than women do. Men also have less sympathy for male victims and consider male sexual assault as less severe than female sexual assault.

Davies and Rogers (2006) also theorized that the average heterosexual man is more homophobic than a woman is. As a result, underlying homophobia accounts for why gay sexual assault victims are judged by others to be more at fault than heterosexual victims. Other studies have shown that heterosexual women and gay men do not express negative views about gay sexual assault compared to male heterosexuals (Davies & Rogers, 2006).

Barriers linked to reporting of sexual assault by African American women stem from the following: myths, self-blame, racism, cultural barriers, stereotypes, distrust in the legal system, and a perceived duty to protect the male Black offender. There are two common myths about African American female assault victims: African American women are loose and, therefore, cannot be raped and only bad girls or bad women are raped. This portrayal has its underpinnings in racism that has also been identified as a

systemic barrier underlying rape myths involving African Americans (Tillman, Bryant-Davis, Smith, & Marks, 2010). Racism has also been identified as a systemic barrier; however, secondary revictimization from the legal system, social services and medical facilities is also a contributing factor (Tillman et al., 2010).

There are cultural barriers to reporting this crime that are long standing and are related to how African American women were repeatedly raped by their slave masters. This created a Jezebel stereotype with false perceptions that African American women today are sexually available (Tillman et al., 2010). Another frequent stereotype is the matriarch stereotype which symbolizes the *strong Black woman* who is independent and self-sufficient (Tillman et al., 2010). This strength is seen as a positive when it comes to resilience when faced with hard times; however, this strength is also seen as a hindrance when a woman is sexually assaulted and is faced with a cultural belief that she should suffer in silence (Tillman et al., 2010).

Women who live in rural areas have identified the following barriers related to their willingness to report being raped: rape myths, stereotypes that men are superior to women, geographic isolation, economic structure, strong social and cultural pressures, and lack of counseling services (Moore, 2009). Additional reasons why some female victims in rural areas do not report the crime of rape include the following: believing rape myths, taking responsibility for the sexual assault, having concern about public exposure, being ashamed and embarrassed, knowing the offender and not wanting the offender to go to jail, and feeling that law enforcement would be insensitive or blame them (Jones et al., 2007).

The effects of not reporting are consistent among all sexual assault victims regardless of cultural or ethnic group. They typically include depression, alcohol use, drug use, and other psychological disorders. Therefore, the importance of confronting and breaking down these barriers must become a priority if sexual assault victims are to receive the help they need.

Facilitators to Reporting Sexual Assault

Although there are obviously many barriers to reporting sexual assault, two key changes in state and federal laws were introduced that aimed to overcome these barriers and facilitate the process of reporting. The federal Violence Against Women Act (VAWA) was first passed in 1994, with reauthorization in 2005 (California Office of Emergency Services [COES], 2012), that created two federal rights for sexual assault victims: (a) the sexual assault victim has the right to a forensic medical exam at no cost to the victim and (b) the sexual assault victim (male or female) has the right to a forensic medical exam without obligation to participate with law enforcement or in the criminal justice proceeding (COES, 2012). The State of California amended previous laws to be in compliance with VAWA requirements by creating and passing Senate Bill 534 (Corbett), which became effective January 1, 2012 (COES, 2012).

According to the COES (2012), the VAWA was created so that more sexual assault victims would then report the crime to law enforcement when they have had time to think about the assault and the need for the perpetrator to be prosecuted. From a health care perspective, the rationale behind this law was the belief that sexual assault victims will seize the opportunity to seek medical care after the assault without the fear of involving law enforcement (COES, 2012). Because of the psychological trauma and the

threats and fears associated with a sexual assault, many survivors do not report.

Therefore, the VAWA and its reauthorization provide an opportunity for sexual assault victims to receive medical attention and the psychological services they need as well as time to think about whether to report and prosecute. It also allows for forensic evidence to be gathered as part of the medical exam and sent to law enforcement where it is preserved and maintained to be used at a later time if the victim decides to press charges (COES, 2012).

Prior to 1971, parents made all medical and legal decisions for their children from birth to 21 years of age until legislation changed the adult legal age from 21 to 18 (Devettere, 2009). Although the legal age is 18, there are federal and state laws that allow minors to give consent for certain types of medical treatment beginning at 12 years old (Devettere, 2009). California law permits emancipated minors and those over the age of 12 to seek treatment for sexually transmitted diseases, prenatal care, drug abuse, contraception, abortion (Devettere, 2009), and/or sexual assault (COES, 2012). California Family Code Sections 6927 and 6928 permit minors ages 12 to 17 to consent to a forensic exam and treatment without parental consent (COES, 2012). Because a minor can consent to a forensic sexual assault exam without parental consent, he or she also has the right to decline the forensic medical exam. In addition, the California Health and Safety Code Sections 123110 (a) and 123115 (a) state that health care providers are not permitted to inform parent(s) or legal guardian(s) of such medical services without the patient's consent. In these special circumstances, the provider can only share a minor's medical record information with the signed consent of the minor (COES, 2012). These laws have been created to protect the rights of adolescent sexual assault victims.

California Penal Code 264.2 is another law that facilitates victim reporting. Penal Code 264.2 states that all victims have the right to a rape crisis advocate and support person of their choice during the sexual assault evidentiary exam or physical exam. This California law requires law enforcement to immediately call the local crisis counseling center when a victim is ready to be transported to a hospital or facility for a sexual assault evidentiary exam or a physical exam. This law allows the victim a support person to aid in his or her recovery for both short-term and long-term counseling (Onecle, 2014).

Sexual Assault Response Teams: Their Role in Sexual Assault Reporting

Victims who are seen at Sexual Assault Response Team (SART) Centers can have a comprehensive medical-legal exam by a trained and specialized Sexual Assault Nurse Examiner (SANE) at no cost to them. SART Centers are equipped to collect forensic evidence as well as meet the medical needs of victims by providing prophylactic treatment to prevent unwanted pregnancy and sexually transmitted infections. Advocacy experts also come to SART Centers to provide crisis and follow-up counseling to meet the psychological needs of victims. They are able to provide both short-term and long-term counseling services at these centers.

The SANE is able to provide assistance to victims during their interactions with the legal system in the following manner: providing a high quality patient-focused exam; encouraging short-term and long-term counseling; acknowledging that the assault was not their fault, as many victims feel guilty and ashamed; providing encouragement and verbalizing strengths that victims demonstrate; educating about injuries and their significance; and educating about anatomy and why there may be no visible signs of physical injury to their anogenital area (Campbell, Greeson, & Patterson, 2011).

SANEs not only provide medical care to victims of sexual assault, but they also interview victims about their assault. They know the importance of their role in supporting victims to report this crime. The combination of empathy, respect, and educating the patient may have a positive effect on victim reporting and cooperating with the legal system (Campbell et al., 2011). A study conducted by Marchetti (2012) involving a sample of 78 women and men supported this theory. Marchetti investigated issues related to the concept of regret when victims report sexual assault to law enforcement. The findings revealed that assault victims conveyed less regret about reporting the incident and there was an increase in reporting when victims sought treatment after the sexual assault (Marchetti, 2012).

SANEs also work to support law enforcement efforts in interviewing sexual assault victims. According to Milne and Bull (2007) and Schwartz (2010), law enforcement education varies widely among police agencies related to victim interview training. Information about interviewing techniques and the necessary skill sets appears in numerous law enforcement training programs (U.S. Department of Justice, 2002); however, education is not evenly disseminated during police training in various law enforcement agencies (Campbell, 1995). The U.S. Department of Justice (2002) suggested the following interviewing considerations: maintain a courteous demeanor, be considerate of privacy issues, grant the victim control during the interview process (e.g., demonstrate active listening and allow the victim to speak with minimal interruptions), avoid traumatizing actions, document the victim's emotional reaction, and give the victim appropriate referrals as soon as possible. These acts are most likely to help increase the

victim's memory of the event and also increase the likelihood that the victim will want to prosecute, which may potentially lead to a conviction.

Victims of sexual assault are at an increased risk for and may suffer from depression, PTSD, and drug and/or alcohol abuse and contemplate suicide long after the incident (Sarkar & Sarkar, 2006). Many victims have encountered major problems with obtaining help for legal aid and mental health and medical care (Campbell, 2008). According to Campbell (2008), two significant reasons women did not seek aid were the victims' belief they would be treated poorly and feelings of uncertainty if they would even find help. In order to help improve the community response to sexual assault, the number of SART Center programs has increased, which have also increased prosecution rates (Campbell, 2008). These programs were created to avoid many of the problems associated with victims seeking medical care through the emergency department by having specialized SANEs who provide crisis intervention and medical care 24/7 (Campbell, 2008). SART programs have SANEs who are specialized in working with sexual assault victims. SANEs emphasize treating victims with empathy and respect in order to reduce postassault psychological distress. In addition, SART programs also work with local rape crisis advocate centers. This patient-centered care allows victim advocates to provide emotional support during the forensic evidentiary exam, along with counseling. This patient-centered care not only helps the psychological well-being of the victim, but the SANE also provides the forensic evidentiary exam and medical care (e.g., prophylactic medication for sexually transmitted infections and pregnancy; Campbell, 2008).

The long-term consequences of not receiving appropriate medical and psychological care postassault are significant; therefore, appropriate referrals are necessary (Campbell, 2008). Multiple resources for sexual assault victims were included in the educational brochure developed for this project. They included emergency hotlines for local rape crisis centers, the local SART Center hotline, and educational websites and advocacy outreach programs throughout the community. This information was included so law enforcement officers would have up-to-date resources to refer victims to for assistance.

Limbic System and Hypothalamic-Pituitary-Adrenal Axis

This next section of the Review of Literature looks at the concepts and research related to the physiologic responses to sexual assault. A brief discussion of the physiology of the limbic system is provided in order to understand the physiologic response to a highly stressful event, such as a sexual assault, and the role of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis in secreting stress hormones. This introduction will assist in understanding the concept of TI as it relates to sexual assault and the victim's varied responses.

The preservation of homeostasis during stress is often facilitated through a highly complex interactive body of neuroanatomical pathways within the brain. In response to stress, neurotransmitters systems initiate physiological, endocrine, metabolic, immune, and behavioral changes in the body (Drolet et al., 2001). One such system that responds to stress is the limbic system. This system has multiple functions, which include adrenaline flow, feelings, behavior, enthusiasm, long-term memory, and sense of smell (Copeland & Gorey, 2012). One's emotions and feelings in life are mainly stored in the

limbic system along with the formation of memories (Copeland & Gorey, 2012). The hippocampus is part of the limbic system and has multiple functions, including its role with other limbic structures to overcome fear responses (Tull, 2014). The hippocampus is also responsible for storing and retrieving memory along with connecting those memories to feelings. When a person recalls a memory, the limbic system is activated and the person can feel the same emotions from when that memory originated. In addition, some memories during trauma may briefly stop working because of a disruption in memory processing. These memories may not be processed or stored as long-term memories and, for these reasons, some parts of a traumatic experience may not be remembered (Kansiewicz, 2013).

The HPA axis is a multifaceted, complex system that helped our ancestors survive life-changing events, such as freezing temperatures, shortage of water, starvations, and threats to social power (Copeland & Gorey, 2012). Even in modern times, the purpose of the HPA axis is still the same and this endocrine system is activated with stress. During a sexual assault, there are changes in the body from this traumatic event that result in an increase in corticotrophin-releasing hormone (CRH), which causes a dysregulation of the HPA axis. As a result, there is a decreased responsiveness to the CRH, which then causes an overactivation of the HPA axis that disturbs the negative feedback with cortisol (Chivers-Wilson, 2006).

In an acute stressful situation, the effects of CRH include the following: activated fear behaviors, heightened arousal, heightened motor activity, increased heart rate and blood pressure, decreased appetite and sexual activity, reduced neurovegetative function, and decreased reward expectations (Southwick, Vythilingam, & Charney, 2005). The

increase effects of cortisol during an acute stress event mobilize the individual, providing energy for fight or flight, heightened arousal, and focused awareness, and also contribute to fear memory formation and fear learning (Southwick et al., 2005). Research has suggested that damage to the HPA axis can also result from early life stressors such as child maltreatment. Damage to the HPA axis causes the HPA axis to dysregulate and become hypersensitive, causing additional cortisol to be distributed in the body, including the brain, which can cause detrimental effects on child development (Joels, 2010).

Opioids and Stress

Endogenous opioid peptides have also been shown to contribute to stress responses (Drolet et al., 2001). A distinct feature of the palliative effects of opioids is the reduction of the distressing, emotional component of pain; however, it does not dull the sensation itself (Drolet et al., 2001). A phenomenon called stress-induced analgesia occurs when a person exhibits stress and experiences relief from pain (Parikh et al., 2011). Hence, opioid peptides may decrease the impact of stress by reducing certain physiologic responses and numbing one's emotional and affective states. As a result, these opioids play a direct role in balancing the response of how the stressor affects the central nervous system by calming or limiting the range of physiologic and emotional responses (Drolet et al., 2001).

Tonic Immobility

The issue of victim consent and indications of struggling during a sexual assault are key considerations when law enforcement investigates a crime (Galliano, Noble, Travis, & Puechl, 1993). The degree to which a victim resists can affect the outcome of jury verdicts and the length of the sentencing. In addition, when there is an increased

level of resistance to the assault by the victim, attitudes of family and friends will focus more on blaming the perpetrator rather than casting doubt on the victim's credibility (Galliano et al., 1993; McCaul, Veltum, Boyechko, & Crawford, 1990).

Two older but benchmark studies provided key information about victims of sexual assault. Meyer and Taylor (1986) reported that sexual assault victims who felt paralyzed or who were passive during the assault experienced the following: more self-blame, guilt, and self-derogation. Stewart et al. (1987) reported that victims were less likely to seek immediate medical treatment when experiencing feelings of paralysis after the attack.

TI has been formally characterized as rape induced paralysis and is a phenomenon that a victim experiences as a self-defense response during a traumatic event (Bados, Toribio, & Garcia-Grau, 2008). Coined phrases depicting this phenomenon include *scared stiff*, *frozen with fear*, and *shell shock*—the term used for military soldiers who become immobilized during combat (S. D. Suarez & Gallup, 1976). According to Gray (1987), four types of self-defense reactions that are experienced by an individual when in danger include the following: alertness, fighting back, escape, and TI. The phenomenon of TI has not been well studied in humans compared to the first three self-defense reactions. TI is described as being frozen in place (i.e., the inability to physically and verbally move one's body), experiencing muscular rigidity, having feelings of coldness, and being numb to the painful stimuli (Bados et al., 2008). These responses are evoked when one is in fear and/or is physically restricted and perceives not being able to escape or have the ability to win the fight.

The premise of this phenomenon has been studied in animals when a predator reacts to the movement of its prey. If the prey does not struggle, the predator may temporarily release its grip, allowing the prey to escape (Marks, 1987; Moskowitz, 2004). According to S. D. Suarez and Gallup (1976), during a rape, assuming an immobile posture can serve at least three immediate purposes: (a) the perpetrator may experience sexual dysfunction and the attack may stop, (b) the amount of physical injury may be minimized because the victim is not struggling, and (c) the victim may have a chance to flee.

A study by Galliano et al. (1993) was the first empirical investigation assessing the similarity between rape-induced paralysis in humans and the similarities of TI from previous animal studies. The TI features from previous animal studies included the following: rigid-like posture, the inability to vocalize, shaking/trembling, closing the eyes, and a lower heart rate (Galliano et al., 1993). Participants included 35 adult rape survivors, from 18 to 61 years of age, who were recruited from a university counseling center and by word of mouth. The time period after a completed rape to the victim's participation in the research study ranged from 2 months to 10 years; 51% of the victims were victimized by strangers, and 89% of the subjects were Caucasian and 11% were Black (Galliano et al., 1993). This group of researchers developed a 31-item survey titled Rape Survivors Questionnaire (RSQ) to assess the following: demographics, exposure to violence (preassault), attitudes and beliefs about rape (preassault and postassault), sensations to the body (physically) during the actual rape, and the victim's behavior immediately postrape and during the following year.

A 7-point Likert-type scale was used in the Galliano et al. (1993) study.

Responses to survey items depicting participants who froze or felt paralyzed revealed that 37% of participants had index scores of 6 or higher (the immobile group), 23% had scores of 5 (the intermediate group), and 40% had scores of 4 or less (the mobile group). The researchers also used a 3-point intensity scale to measure behaviors observed in previous animal studies about TI, which included the following behaviors: (a) motor inhibition, (b) trembling, (c) closing the eyes, (d) increased rate of breathing, and (e) feeling cold. The results revealed that the immobile group underwent these five different experiences to a larger degree ($M = 2.0$) than the intermediate group ($M = 1.2$) and the mobile group ($M = 1.1$), $F(2, 32) = 4.08, p < .05$. The results of the Galliano et al. study suggest that a sexual assault victim may experience TI behaviors similar to those TI behaviors seen in animals.

Galliano et al. (1993) also found a significant association between frequency in life changes after an assault and being immobile, $X^2(2, N = 35) = 31.55, p < .05$, and an increased number of life changes in the mobile group than experienced by the immobile group. Lastly, a 2 x 2 ANOVA showed the following: (a) belief by the victim that the assault could have been stopped if she had used greater resistance (immobile group— $M = 4.0$; mobile group— $M = 2.2$), $F(2, 64) = 4.67, p < .05$, and (b) a belief that more people would believe the victim was raped if the victim had used greater resistance (immobile group— $M = 3.8$; mobile group— $M = 2.8$), $F(2, 64) = 3.83, p < .05$ (Galliano et al., 1993). The abovementioned results all demonstrate the negative impact on recovering after rape for victims who experience immobility (Galliano et al., 1993).

Heidt, Marx, and Forsyth (2005) looked at TI in childhood sexual abuse (CSA) victims using the Tonic Immobility Scale-Child Abuse Form (TIS-C) developed by Forsyth, Marx, Heidt, Fuse, and Gallup (2000, as cited in Heidt et al., 2005). The study participants consisted of 80 females; 39 were undergraduate students taking an introductory psychology course at a large Northeastern university, while the other 41 participants were psychiatric inpatients receiving care at a large medical center in the Northeastern United States. The undergraduate students were selected from their responses on a screening instrument, namely, the Posttraumatic Diagnostic Inventory, which asked about traumatic childhood events. Initially, 603 completed the Posttraumatic Diagnostic Inventory. Seventy-one of the participants experienced CSA and agreed to be contacted for follow-up; eight of the 71 could not be reached, 16 declined to participate, and eight were dropped due to incomplete records, leaving 39 participants. Subjects selected from the inpatient pool were initially screened by a psychiatrist about prior victimization upon their admission to the hospital unit. Initially, 48 females were contacted; however, three declined to participate, two discontinued their participation, and two were dropped because of incomplete records.

Subjects in the Heidt et al. (2005) study completed the following: the Beck Depression Inventory; the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory, Form-Y; the Posttraumatic Diagnostic Scale; the Peritraumatic Dissociative Experiences Questionnaire-Self Report; the Life Experiences Questionnaire; and the Tonic Immobility Scale-Child Abuse Form (TIS-C). The TIS-C results were the most relevant to the Heidt et al. project. The TIS-C is made up of 30 questions with two categories. The first category includes 13 questions which examine and measure TI responses. The first 10 of the 13 items assess the

following: the inability to move while not being restrained, feeling frozen, not being able to vocalize or call out, numbness, and being detached from one's self. Items 11 and 12 examine psychological events, assessing memory of the event and guilt/shame feelings. Item 13 requires a yes/no response and assesses whether the individual had experiences during a sexual assault similar to those addressed in Items 1-12. Items 1-12 use a 7-point Likert-type scale with a range of scores from 0 to 6. The second part of the TIS-C survey consists of 17 items examining behaviors of the victim and perpetrator (i.e., paralysis, unmanageable shaking, not being able to call out, and fear of and anger at the perpetrator after immobility). Part 2 of the survey has seven items that involve a 7-point Likert-type response scale with a range of scores from 0 to 6 and the remaining questions require yes/no answers. They examined detailed aspects of assaults (e.g., eye contact with perpetrator, restrained, and beaten). In the Heidt et al. study, the second part of the TIS-C survey was only to be completed if participants felt frozen during the assault. Because Part 1 yielded higher scores for TI symptomatology, the researchers did not analyze the results for Part 2 of their study.

The following findings in the Heidt et al. (2005) study were statistically significant: inpatients were older ($M = 32.75$, $SD = 7.88$) than undergraduates ($M = 21.36$, $SD = 7.65$), $p < .001$, and greater numbers of ethnic minorities composed the inpatient group, $X^2(5, N = 80) = 20.06$, $p < .001$. Inpatients also suffered more from depression, anxiety, PTSD symptomatology ($p < .001$) and peritraumatic dissociation ($p = .002$) compared to undergraduates. In addition, Heidt et al. revealed that the onset of CSA began at 3 to 17 years of age, with a mean age of 9.92 years ($SD = 4.22$). The age of the perpetrator was 7 to 60 years old, with a mean age of 24.65 years ($SD = 13.27$). The

difference in age between the perpetrator and the victim ranged from 2 years to 50 years of age, with a mean difference of 14.76 years ($SD = 14.29$).

Of the 80 subjects in the Heidt et al. (2005) study, 52.5% of the victims experienced TI. The researchers examined both TI and fear. Fear was included because previous research showed that extreme fear together with entrapment and/or physical restraint are needed to produce TI. TI and fear were plotted on a y- and x-axis, respectively. Scores on TI had a range from 0 to 42, with a midpoint of 21, whereas scores on fear had a range from 0 to 18, with a midpoint of 9. TI was defined as having scores equal to and greater for both TI and fear, with midpoints of 21 and 9, respectively. Participants who scored less than 21 on TI and less than 9 on fear were classified as the non-TI group, which represented 47.5% of the subjects. A chi-square analysis revealed that 72.5% of the inpatient group was classified in the TI group compared to the undergraduates (33.3%), $X^2(1, N = 79) = 12.17, p < .001$. The researchers also classified the participants into the following: Group 1, victims who reported CSA that did not involve rape or attempted rape, and Group 2, those who were raped or experienced an attempted rape. Group 2 represented 73% of the 80 participants. As hypothesized, Group 2 had a higher rate of TI (62.1%) than Group 1 (28.6%), $X^2(1, N = 79) = 6.95, p < .01$. Heidt et al. conducted bivariate correlations between psychological distress and TI and fear. The findings showed positive correlations between TI and fear and increased reports of depression, anxiety, PTSD, and peritraumatic dissociation ($p < .01$). Another bivariate correlation showed positive correlations between age difference between the perpetrator and victim and both TI, $r = .27, p < .02$, and fear scores, $r = .39, p < .001$.

Heidt et al.'s (2005) study supported that a majority of CSA victims experienced TI. This study provided evidence-based research that TI is not just experienced in adult sexual assault, as indicated by Galliano et al. (1993), but also with CSA. Heidt et al.'s study also demonstrated that study participants in Group 2 who reported an attempted rape or actual rape had a higher rate of TI than Group 1. Lastly, the results supported that there were increased psychological symptoms with increased TI.

Because of the phenomenon of TI that may occur during a sexual assault, information about TI was included in the brochure to educate law enforcement on its manifestations. Law enforcement officers investigate for evidence of obvious signs of resistance when deciding whether a sexual assault has occurred. When these signs are missing, it is more difficult to convince investigators that a sexual assault occurred (Galliano et al., 1993). Furthermore, victims experience additional trauma related to self-shame and guilt by imagining they could have done more or prevented the sexual assault if they had reacted differently (Metzger, 1976; Notman & Nadelson, 1976) as they too are not familiar with the phenomenon of TI. If the victim was informed of these physiological responses, conceivably, the victim may not experience the magnitude of self-blame (S. D. Suarez & Gallup, 1976).

Synthesis of Research Literature

The overall consensus from the articles reviewed for this project is that sexual assault is an underreported crime, and identifying the barriers is important in order to develop strategies to promote reporting by victims. Rape myth acceptance appears to be a leading barrier, with evidence indicating that men exhibit a significantly higher agreement with rape myth acceptance than women (E. Suarez & Gadalla, 2010). In

addition, the review of literature also supports that the barriers to reporting sexual assault are complex from shame and embarrassment to fear of the perpetrator, along with racial and cultural barriers. Facilitators to sexual assault reporting include supporting federal and state laws for victims of sexual assault. These laws include the VAWA, California Penal Code 264.2, and California Family Code Sections 6927 and 6928, all of which enable victims to report the sexual assault with greater ease by giving them more choices and more rights. Other facilitators include an increase in SART programs with specialized SANEs who are qualified in conducting forensic evidentiary exams.

Appropriate referral sources and resources are needed for sexual assault victims for both short-term and long-term counseling in order to counteract the negative psychological effects associated with sexual assault. In addition, the review of literature explained the physiological responses of the limbic system, which include the fight or flight response, and how certain hormones and chemicals can impair memory and cause various emotional responses by the sexual assault victim. TI, previously known as rape induced paralysis, is a phenomenon that is typically experienced by sexual assault victims as a self-defense response. Victims are often paralyzed and unable to vocalize and experience muscular rigidity, feelings of coldness, and numbness to the painful stimuli (Bados et al., 2008). As a result of these physiological responses experienced by sexual assault victims, it was judged important to include this information in the educational tool designed for this project. Hopefully, first responders will become more knowledgeable of these responses when working with sexual assault victims.

Gaps in the Literature

The literature search undertaken for this project did not reveal any articles that addressed specific reporting barriers reported by Hispanic and Asian groups. In order to become more knowledgeable about barriers to reporting, emails were sent to two local community agencies who served Hispanic and Asian populations asking staff to identify what they believed were typical barriers to sexual assault reporting for victims who sought assistance from their agency. The two advocate agencies contacted were Peace Over Violence and the Center for Pacific Asian Family. Peace Over Violence provides services for sexual assault victims in the San Gabriel Valley and the City of Los Angeles; their clients are representative of all races. The Center for Pacific Asian Family provides counseling for Asian Pacific Islanders. By utilizing these resources, this researcher maximized the knowledge bank needed to create an educational brochure that would encompass many ethnic-cultural barriers.

Cultural and other related barriers affecting the Asian Pacific Islander communities consist of the following: gender roles (e.g., family patriarchy, loyalty to abuser, belief about finding solutions internally, lack of family support, and viewing women as property), tradition (e.g., fear of judgment by others, the custom of keeping problems within the family, and the need to save face), resources (e.g., language barrier, lack of information/knowledge about sexual assault resources, location, and transportation), and government/legal concerns (e.g., fear of deportation, refugee and PTSD, and mistrust of the legal system; K. Kelly, Center for Pacific Asian Family, personal communication, February 22, 2014).

The Hispanic community is also affected by cultural and other barriers. Reported barriers include the following: religious beliefs, language, fear of law enforcement, and fear that no one will believe the victim was raped. Sexual assault victims are also afraid of their assailant for many reasons, including threats by the perpetrator, the assailant may be a relative and the victim fears the rape will break up the family, issues of low self-esteem, prior sexual assault, the victim drinking and not recalling all events, the victim assuming responsibility for the rape, and the victim not being aware of services available for victims (A. Corona, Peace Over Violence, personal communication, March 23, 2014).

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this project.

1. What effect did the educational training using the brochure, *Sexual Assault Reporting: Guide for First Responders*, as a teaching tool have on law enforcement officers' rape myth acceptance scores from baseline pretesting to posttesting?
2. How did rape myth acceptance scores for the pretest differ between those who completed only the pretest and those who completed both the pretest and posttest?
3. What effect did demographic variables (i.e., age, gender, education, and race) have on rape myth acceptance scores from pretesting to posttesting?
4. What effect did knowing any sexual assault victims (including friends, family members, coworkers, and/or self) have on rape myth acceptance scores from pretesting to posttesting?

5. Did rank, years in law enforcement, and work experience (e.g., sexual assault cases, shift work, and training) influence rape myth acceptance scores from pretest to posttest?

METHODS

Design

A pretest-posttest quantitative research design was chosen to evaluate the effectiveness of the education tool and training session in reducing rape myth acceptance among law enforcement officers participating in this pilot project. The evaluation process consisted of multiple phases including a pretest; an educational training using a brochure, *Sexual Assault Reporting: Guide for First Responders*, created by the researcher (see Appendix C); and a posttest. Phase 1 involved a pretest, namely Quiz 1, which explored the rape myth acceptance views of police officers about victims of sexual assault or rape. Phase 2 involved an educational training session using a brochure created by the researcher that discussed the following topics: rape myths, sexual assault data, barriers and facilitators in sexual assault reporting, community resources, and the neurobiology of brain trauma caused by the sexual assault. After dissemination of the brochure, along with the training, a posttest, namely Quiz 2, was given to evaluate the effectiveness of the brochure and training.

Protection of Human Rights

This project involved human subjects who were asked to participate in this project by attending an educational session; reviewing the content of a brochure designed for the project, titled *Sexual Assault Reporting: Guide for First Responders*; and completing both a pretest and posttest. Subjects were recruited from a group of law enforcement officers employed by a Southern California police department. Approvals were, therefore, obtained from the California State University of Long Beach Institutional Review Board and from the commanding officers of the police department participating in this project.

Each officer was provided two consent forms for Quiz 1 and Quiz 2 (see Appendices D and E) seeking their consent to participate as a volunteer in this study.

Subjects

The subjects in this study consisted of law enforcement officers from one Southwestern United States police department whose ranks varied from patrol officers to commanding officers. These participants were chosen because they were law enforcement officers who were first responders to rape and sexual assault victims. The inclusion criteria for this study consisted of being a sworn police officer who agreed to participate in this research study. The only officer excluded from participating in this study was the training officer who approved the training. This officer was not able to participate nor be present during said training to eliminate participants feeling potential coercion bias. The study involved officers on seven different rotating shifts, with the number of recruitments based on the number of officers on shift that day. The approved training conducted by the researcher was a mandatory training for the officers; however, their participation in completing pretest Quiz 1 and posttest Quiz 2 was voluntary.

Setting

The training related to the brochure took place in the briefing room in the police department at the beginning of their work shifts scheduled at 7:30 a.m., 1:30 p.m., and 7:30 p.m. Law enforcement officers were instructed to complete both quizzes in a private area, preferably at home, and not at the station.

Development of the Brochure

The educational brochure used in this study was developed to address the myths, barriers, and facilitators associated with sexual assault as reported in the literature.

Statistics about the incidence of sexual assault and a list of resources to assist victims were also included to provide an overview of the enormity of this problem. In addition, the neurobiology of brain trauma addressing the limbic system, the HPA axis, and the concept of TI were also included. The graphics of the brochure were designed to be esthetically and culturally appropriate and the layout of content was done to create a reader-friendly tool. After several iterations, the content, layout, and organization of the brochure were evaluated by expert review panels to determine content validity.

The outside of the brochure is titled, *Sexual Assault Reporting: Guide for First Responders*. The inside of the eight-panel brochure consists of the following: myths and facts about sexual assault, along with barriers to reporting. The back of the brochure explains the limbic system, TI, supporting laws, and effective interviewing and has a to-do list, a list of resources with the SART Center name and phone number, rape and battery hotline contacts and other advocacy hotlines, and websites.

Expert Evaluation of the Brochure

An Expert Evaluation tool was developed by the project investigator to guide a panel of experts in their assessment of the tool's (i.e., the brochure) content validity, design, and organization. Multiple experts who work with sexual assault victims as part of the multidisciplinary SART team were asked to be on the expert review panels. The following experts were included in the review panel based on their area of expertise and knowledge of myths, barriers, and facilitators of sexual abuse reporting: SANEs who have specialized training in performing sexual assault exams, with the goal of collecting potential evidence and helping patients with their medical and emotional needs; advocacy experts who work directly with sexual assault victims for short-term and long-term

counseling and are very instrumental in patients' emotional well-being; sex crime detectives who are first responders and experts in interviewing victims, witnesses, and criminals; and deputy district attorneys who make the final decision about bringing cases to trial. The first draft of the tool was sent out with a scoring sheet and served as a preliminary evaluation of the brochure. Feedback was given and the tool went through several iterations. A final draft was distributed via email to the same groups of experts with expanded scoring (see Appendix F) and responses were collected.

The experts were asked to respond to 14 questions related to the tool's content accuracy, relevancy, and value of subject area content presented in the brochure; visual appeal related to format and layout; organization of content; and professional presentation of material. Twelve experts were queried and 12 responded. A Likert-type scale using a 1-5 rating scale for each of the 14 questions, with 1 being *poor* or *not valuable* and 5 as *excellent* or *very valuable* was used. A higher score indicated a more accurate and higher quality brochure. The maximum total score representing all 14 items was 70; the mean score of the experts was 67.58, with a range of 56 to 70. The highest possible individual score for each item was 5; the range of scores on the items was 3 to 5, with mean scores on individual items ranging from 4.67 to 4.92. The individual item scores for the evaluation tool were judged to be satisfactory as a score of 4 on the Likert-type scale was either *very good* or *valuable*; all scores were at or above 4.67. There was a 96.5% agreement among the expert panel.

Instruments

This project focused on addressing the problem of rape acceptance myths and their impact on reporting of sexual abuse through the creation of an educational brochure

for first responders. Three separate tools were used in this project. The first tool (Expert Evaluation) was created to assess the validity, reliability, and usefulness of the educational brochure. The results of the brochure evaluation were addressed previously. The second tool used was the Updated Illinois Rape Myth Acceptance Scale, and the third instrument was a modified version of the Updated Illinois Rape Myth Acceptance Scale. The Updated Illinois Rape Myth Acceptance Scale and the modified the Updated Illinois Rape Myth Acceptance Scale were used to assess the effectiveness of the educational tool and training session in reducing rape myth acceptance among the law enforcement officers participating in this study.

Investigating the perceptions of officers' rape myths, barriers, and facilitators was an important element of this project. Because the Updated Illinois Rape Myth Acceptance Scale is a known valid and reliable instrument, it was used to assess law enforcement officers' perceptions of rape myths prior to the education session. It became the pretest, namely, Quiz 1 (see Appendix D). Next, a decision was made by the DNP project author to modify the Updated Illinois Rape Myth Acceptance Scale for the posttest, namely Quiz 2. This modification was done in order to create an illusion of taking a different test while evaluating the same questions and answers from Quiz 1. The tool was altered by adding 11 questions throughout the survey. These additional questions are numbers 1, 2, 7, 10, 11, 14, 17, 20, 23, 27, and 33 (see Appendix E). The following statements were included at the end of Quiz 2: "End of Session. You have now completed the survey. I would like to thank you for your participation for this research project," "Modified by Toyetta Beukes," and "(Payne, Lonsway, & Fitzgerald, 1999; McMahon & Farmer, 2011)."

The pretest and posttest consisted of questions related to rape myths, with responses grouped into a 5-point Likert-type scale, with 1 being *strongly agree* and 5 being *strongly disagree*. A lower score indicated a higher rate of rape myth acceptance. The researcher utilized the Updated Illinois Rape Myth Acceptance Scale for both the pretest and posttest, namely Quiz 1 and Quiz 2. However, Quiz 2 scores were used as a surrogate measure of the effectiveness of the tool. Quiz 1 included the following: informed consent with a waived signature; four deidentified questions to connect Quiz 1 and Quiz 2; demographic information including age, gender, race, years of experience, officer rank, number of sexual assault cases handled during the officer's career, number of sexual assault training sessions attended, highest level of education, any known victims, start time of work shift; and the 22 survey questions from the Updated Illinois Rape Myth Acceptance Scale developed by McMahon and Farmer (2011). The researcher eliminated the name Updated Illinois Rape Myth Acceptance Scale from Quiz 1. All four subscale headings that appeared in the original form of this tool were eliminated, which consisted of the following titles: "She asked for it," "He didn't mean to," "It wasn't really rape," and "She lied." Finally, the scoring system on the bottom of the survey was likewise removed.

The law enforcement officer's age, gender, race, years of experience, questions relating to sexual assault training, work and personal experience, rank, how many sexual assault cases in the officer's law enforcement career, how many sexual assault training sessions, education, any known victims, and start of work shift were included to analyze for possible covariate relationships. As a strategy to reduce the pretest effect for Quiz 2,

the researcher varied the two tests by adding 11 new questions to Quiz 2. These 11 questions were eliminated during the analysis.

The Illinois Rape Myth Acceptance Scale is a 45-item scale that looks at rape myth acceptance attitudes. This tool was originally created by Payne, Lonsway, and Fitzgerald (1999) and validated using a sample of 604 undergraduate college students, with an overall reliability score of .93; subscale alphas varied from .74 to .84 (Payne et al., 1999). The Illinois Rape Myth Acceptance Scale was then revised to the 22-item scale by McMahon and Farmer (2011), which was used in this project.

The Updated Illinois Rape Myth Acceptance Scale evaluates rape myth acceptance by using more current, modernized language and denoting more understated rape myths. The researcher obtained permission by McMahon and Farmer to utilize the Updated Illinois Rape Myth Acceptance Scale as a tool as it has been verified through multiple studies and used successfully (see Appendix G). The tool was analyzed for reliability by sampling 951 undergraduate students in a northeastern university. Construct validity was examined using exploratory structural equation modeling (ESEM). Criterion validity was assessed using the multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) with Multiple Indicators Multiple Causes (MIMIC) modeling added to the evaluation of the Updated Illinois Rape Myth Acceptance Scale. Results as reported by authors McMahon and Farmer (2011) provide the analytical support for criterion validity of this updated measure.

Procedures

The following procedures were implemented after approval from the Institutional Review Board and the police department where the project took place. The project had

two phases involving a pretest and posttest, namely Quiz 1 and Quiz 2, respectfully. The first phase involved the researcher passing out Quiz 1 (described in Instruments) and a blank envelope, labeled Quiz 1, in a sealed envelope to 86 subjects.

During Phase 1, the subjects were asked to take the sealed packet and open it in a private area, preferably their home. Upon reading the informed consent with instructions, the participants then decided to participate or not. If they agreed, the participants then completed Quiz 1 and placed it in a sealed envelope, labeled Quiz 1, and placed said envelope in a secured bin at the police station. If law enforcement officers decided not to participate, they had the option to return the blank packet and/or blank quiz inside the envelope as described above so not to feel separated or left out. The DNP project author returned throughout the week to collect the envelopes.

The second phase involved the DNP author returning the following week to conduct the approved training using her brochure, *Sexual Assault Reporting: Guide for First Responders*, as the focus of the presentation. After said training, the 84 subjects were given Quiz 2 to complete in a private area, preferably their home, and return it in a sealed envelope, labeled Quiz 2, and place it in a secured bin at the police department. For both Quiz 1 and Quiz 2, the informed consent signatures were waived.

Script

The researcher established a schedule with the training officer to conduct 14 sessions divided into two phases. The roll-call trainings were scheduled on rotating shifts at 7:30 a.m., 1:30 p.m., and 7:30 p.m., Monday through Sunday. In order to create consistency, the researcher conducted each of these trainings utilizing Script 1 and Script 2 (see Appendices H and I).

This research study involved multiple phases, which were needed to safeguard and protect the privacy and confidentiality of the participants. The first phase was conducted during the first week, with a total of seven sessions. Each session began with introductions and instructions using Script 1 (see Appendix H). The instructions for Phase 1 took 5 minutes and officers were told that Quiz 1, the pretest, would take 15 minutes. Subjects were asked to return Quiz 1 in the sealed envelope that was provided and place it in a secured bin during that week. The secured bin was placed at the entrance of the roll-call briefing room inside an open cabinet. This made it easily accessible to all subjects.

The researcher returned a week later to conduct Phase 2 of the study, which consisted of seven sessions, including the training and posttest, Quiz 2. Similar to Phase 1, Phase 2 began with introductions and instructions using Script 2 (see Appendix I). The training utilized the brochure that was created. The training took 25 minutes, with an additional 5 minutes of questions and answers that followed. As instructed, law enforcement officers were given Quiz 2 in a sealed packet to complete in a private area and return it that week and place it in the secured bin at the police department.

The DNP author again returned throughout the week to collect these documents. Quiz 2 (see Appendix E) was given to assess their understanding regarding the myths, barriers, and facilitators of sexual assault reporting. Quiz 2 should have taken approximately 15 minutes to complete. The results of the posttest were then used to evaluate the efficacy of the brochure and training.

Data Analysis

An Excel data collection tool was created for inputting data from Quiz 1 and Quiz 2. Responses to Quiz 1 and Quiz 2 were coded and entered into an Excel program for analysis. Scores from both quizzes were then used to compare pretesting and posttesting results as a tool to evaluate the usefulness and effectiveness of the training sessions and the brochure. Data from the Demographic Information survey were inputted and analyzed to determine whether there was a relationship between test scores and demographic variables such as age, gender, race, years as a law enforcement officer, rank, number of sexual assault cases investigated, number of sexual assault training sessions, education, how many sexual assault victims the officer knew (including self), and work shift. Descriptive statistics were run using MANOVA to analyze the difference in mean scores with standard deviations from the 19 officers who took the pretest and posttest as well as comparing these same 19 officers to the 26 officers who took only the pretest, whereas a multivariate analysis of covariance (MANCOVA) was used to analyze the mean scores of the covariates (e.g., age, gender, education, race, and so forth).

RESULTS

A total of 86 law enforcement officers were given the opportunity to participate in Phase 1 of the project's pretesting. Of the 86, 45 (52%) officers participated by completing the pretest. In the following week, Phase 2, 85 officers participated in the educational training and had the opportunity to take the posttest; however, only 23 (27%) officers responded by completing the posttest. Of the 23 officers, 19 had completed both the pretest and posttest, whereas the other four officers only completed the posttest. The latter four were not included in any statistical analysis.

Table 5 lists the demographic profile and worked-related experience of the 19 officers who completed both the pretest and posttest. Twenty-six percent ($n = 5$) of the participants were female, whereas the male officers made up 74% ($n = 14$). The age range was from 20 to 55 years. Forty-two percent ($n = 8$) were between the ages of 41 and 50 and another 26% ($n = 5$) were between the ages of 51 and 55. The educational range for the officers varied from a high school/general equivalency diploma (GED) education to a master's degree/doctorate; however, 68% ($n = 13$) had an associate's, a bachelor's, or a master's degree, whereas 26% ($n = 5$) had attended some college. The racial makeup varied from being Caucasian, Latino or Hispanic, Asian American or Pacific Islander, Filipino, Black or African American, or Other. The Latino or Hispanic officers made up almost half of the officers at 47% ($n = 9$), and 26% ($n = 5$) were Caucasian officers. These 19 officers varied in their number of years working in law enforcement, ranging from 6 months to 2 years to more than 21 years. Over half of the officers (53%; $n = 10$) had more than 21 years of experience. Sexual assault training varied from officers reporting no training to having participated in 11 to 15 trainings. Over half of the officers

Table 5

Demographic Profile and Work Experience of Law Enforcement Officers (N = 19)

Demographic	<i>n</i>	%
Gender		
Female	5	26
Male	14	74
Age (groups)		
20-25	1	5
31-35	3	16
36-40	2	11
41-45	4	21
46-50	4	21
51-55	5	26
Education		
High school/GED	1	5
Some college	5	26
Associate's degree	5	26
Bachelor's degree	7	37
Master's degree/doctorate	1	5
Race		
White	5	26
Latino or Hispanic	9	47
Asian American/Pacific Islander	1	5
Filipino American	1	5
Black or African American	2	11
Other	1	5
Years in Law Enforcement		
6 months-2 years 11 months	3	16
3-6 years 11 months	1	5
7-10 years 11 months	3	16
11-15 years 11 months	1	5
16-20 years 11 months	1	5
21 years +	10	53
Sexual Assault Training		
No training	2	11
1-5 trainings	11	58
6-10 trainings	5	26
11-15 trainings	1	5

(58%; $n = 11$) had 1-5 trainings and 26% ($n = 5$) had 6-10 trainings. The demographic profile and work-related experience were not reported for the 26 officers who completed the pretest only as the main focus of this study was to evaluate the effectiveness of the brochure and training.

To gain a better understanding of law enforcement's views on rape myth acceptance and to evaluate the effectiveness of the brochure, *Sexual Assault Reporting: Guide for First Responders*, and the educational sessions held with law enforcement to review the content of this brochure, five research questions were addressed.

The first research question was, "What effect did the educational training using the brochure, *Sexual Assault Reporting: Guide for First Responders*, as a teaching tool have on rape myth acceptance scores from baseline pretesting to posttesting?" To determine this, the individual item scores of the 22 questions for the 19 participants who completed both Quiz 1 and Quiz 2 were compared using MANOVA. Results are presented in Appendix J. In analyzing the overall scores for the pretest to posttest differences, Wilks' lambda testing was conducted. The p value using the Wilks' lambda test was .187, which is greater than .05. Therefore, the multivariate testing did not reveal any statistical difference from the overall pretest to posttest scores.

The next step in the analysis was to investigate the second research question—"How did rape myth acceptance scores for the pretest differ between those who completed only the pretest and those who completed both pretesting and posttesting?" A MANOVA was used to answer this question. In this case, scores from all 45 participants were compared to those of the 19 who completed both Quiz 1 and Quiz 2. This was done

to determine if there were any differences in scores for the 26 participants who did not participate in the posttest. In comparing these two separate groups, this researcher was investigating any similarities or differences that may explain the attrition. The p value from the Wilks' lambda testing was .41, which is greater than .05; therefore, the results of the multivariate analysis indicated no significant difference in the pretest scores of those who took only the pretest from those who took both the pretest and posttest.

The third question of interest was, "What effect did demographic variables (i.e., age, gender, education, and race) have on rape myth acceptance scores from pretesting to posttesting?" To answer this question, a MANCOVA was calculated. The variables (i.e., age, gender, education, and race) were treated as covariates in the model. The dependent variable was the rape myth acceptance scores from the 19 subjects who completed both the pretest and posttest.

The first covariate analyzed was age. There were small numbers in the cell size, making it difficult to suggest any specific conclusion that would be meaningful using parametric statistics. Instead, refer to Table 6 for the average mean scores for each group for the pretest and posttest. The rape myth acceptance scores revealed slightly different scores among the different age groupings of the law enforcement officers. The rape myth acceptance score was calculated by obtaining the mean score for all 22 questions and then comparing the means scores of the various age groups. One can determine which age group has the lowest total score (associated with a higher rape myth acceptance) and which age group has the highest total score (less rape myth acceptance) for the 22 questions. The 20-25 age group ($n = 1$) had the lowest average score for both the pretest and posttest, which suggests a higher rape myth acceptance compared to members in the

other age groups. In contrast, the 36-40 age group ($n = 2$) had the highest average score, which translated that this age group had a higher rate of rejecting rape myths or had less rape myth acceptance. As noted previously, the cell sizes were small and, therefore, no assumptions could be made as to the effect of age on rape myth acceptance for this sample of law enforcement officers.

Table 6

Law Officers' Overall Rape Myth Acceptance Pretest and Posttest Mean Scores by Age Group

Age	$N = 19$	Pretest Mean	Posttest Mean
20-25	1	3.14	3.59
31-35	3	4.28	4.62
36-40	2	4.59	4.71
41-45	4	3.89	4.14
46-50	4	3.91	4.11
51-55	5	3.53	3.85

Note. 5-point Likert-type scale for rape myth acceptance scores—1 = *Strongly Agree*, 5 = *Strongly Disagree*. Lower scores = greater rape myth acceptance. Higher scores = greater rejection of rape myths.

The covariate gender was examined (five females and 14 males). The p value of gender was .14; therefore, the factor of gender was not significant. The covariate education had a p value of .03, indicating that education was associated with significant differences in rape myth acceptance (see Table 7). The results suggested that the associate's degree group ($n = 5$) had the lowest average score for both the pretest and posttest, whereas the high school/GED group ($n = 1$) had the highest mean score, which indicated a higher rejection of rape myth acceptance.

The next covariate race had a p value of .0089, denoting that the factor of race was significant in rape myth acceptance (see Table 8). The subject who marked Other ($n = 1$) for race had the lowest average score on both the pretest and posttest, whereas the

subject ($n = 1$) who was Asian American or Pacific Islander had the highest score on the pretest and the subjects ($n = 2$) who were Black or African American had the highest scores on the posttest.

Table 7

Law Officers' Overall Rape Myth Acceptance Pretest and Posttest Mean Scores by Highest Level of Education Achieved

Education	$N = 19$	Pretest	Posttest
High School/GED	1	4.86	4.91
Some college	5	3.92	4.13
Associate's degree	5	3.63	3.85
Bachelor's degree	7	3.94	4.25
Master's degree/doctorate	1	3.82	4.68

Note. 5-point Likert-type scale for rape myth acceptance scores—1 = *Strongly Agree*, 5 = *Strongly Disagree*. Lower scores = greater rape myth acceptance. Higher scores = greater rejection of rape myths.

Table 8

Law Officers' Overall Rape Myth Acceptance Pretest and Posttest Scores by Race

Race	$N = 19$	Pretest	Posttest
White	5	3.97	4.35
Latino or Hispanic	9	3.81	3.99
Asian Pacific Islander	1	4.59	3.83
Filipino American	1	4.32	4.08
Black or African American	2	4.32	4.73
Other	1	3.44	3.44

Note. 5-point Likert-type scale for rape myth acceptance scores—1 = *Strongly Agree*, 5 = *Strongly Disagree*. Lower scores = greater rape myth acceptance. Higher scores = greater rejection of rape myths.

Question 4 asked, “What effect did knowing any sexual assault victims, including friends, family members, coworkers, and/or self, have on rape myth acceptance scores from pretesting to posttesting?” The findings showed that knowing sexual assault victims had a significant impact ($p = .005$) on rape myth acceptance scores from pretesting to posttesting as the scores had increased, showing a greater rejection of rape myths.

Question 5 asked, “Did rank, years in law enforcement, and work experience (e.g., sexual assault cases, shift work, and training) influence rape myth acceptance scores from pretest to posttest?” In analyzing the effect of rank on scores, rank was categorized into the following three groups: law enforcement or training officer; detective or corporal; and sergeant, lieutenant, captain, commanding officer, or chief. There was no statistically significant difference in mean scores ($p = .119$). However, with regard to years in law enforcement, the analysis revealed a p value of .012 (see Table 9). In the pretest, subjects ($n = 3$) in the 7-10 years 11 months group had the highest score, which translated to a higher rejection of rape myths. However, the subject ($n = 1$) in the 16-20 years 11 months group had the lowest score (i.e., a higher rape myth acceptance). Similarly, subjects ($n = 3$) in the 7-10 years 11 months group also scored highest in posttesting and the 3-6 years 11 months group ($n = 1$) had the lowest score. Overwhelmingly, 53% ($n = 10$) of law enforcement officers had greater than 21 years of experience. Their pretest and posttest scores went from 3.76 to 4.05, respectively, an increase of 0.29.

Table 9

Law Enforcement Officers' Overall Rape Myth Acceptance Pretest and Posttest Scores by Years Working as a Law Enforcement Officer

Years working in Law Enforcement	$N = 19$	Pretest	Posttest
6 months-2 years 11 months	3	3.90909	4.196970
3-6 years 11 months	1	3.45455	3.227273
7-10 years 11 months	3	4.46970	4.833333
11-15 years 11 months	1	3.83636	4.681818
16-20 years 11 months	1	3.10455	3.727273
21 years +	10	3.75909	4.045455

Note. 5-point Likert-type scale for rape myth acceptance scores—1 = *Strongly Agree*, 5 = *Strongly Disagree*. Lower scores = greater rape myth acceptance. Higher scores = greater rejection of rape myths.

In examining law enforcement's work experience in conducting sexual assault cases and shift work, the p values were .16387 and .05872, respectively, which was greater than .05, so these factors were not significant in this population with a small sample size. In contrast, law enforcement training was significant, with a p value of .0017 (see Table 10). Therefore, subjects ($n = 5$) who had 6-10 trainings had the lowest average scores for both the pretest and posttest, whereas subjects ($n = 2$) who had no training had the highest average scores for both tests. The latter group had a higher rate of rejecting rape myths.

Table 10

Law Enforcement Officer's Rape Myth Acceptance Pretest and Posttest Scores by the Number of Sexual Assault Training Courses

Number of Trainings	$N = 19$	Pretest	Posttest
No training	2	4.272727	4.681818
1-5 trainings	11	3.958678	4.185950
6-10 trainings	5	3.627273	3.845455
11-15 trainings	1	3.772727	4.545455

Note. 5-point Likert-type scale for rape myth acceptance scores—1 = *Strongly Agree*, 5 = *Strongly Disagree*. Lower scores = greater rape myth acceptance. Higher scores = greater rejection of rape myths.

DISCUSSION AND SUMMARY

Rape myth acceptance attitudes were assessed in 45 law enforcement officers, 19 of whom completed both the pretest and posttest as part of an educational training session discussing the content of a brochure, *Sexual Assault Reporting: Guide for First Responders*, that addressed rape myths as well as barriers and facilitators to reporting a sexual assault. Several variables including age, gender, education, and race were evaluated. First, a comparison of 19 pretest scores to posttest scores was done. Although the mean scores of 18 of the 22 items in the Updated Illinois Rape Myth Acceptance Scale consistently increased, the overall mean score of rape myth acceptance from pretesting to posttesting was not statistically significant. However, the posttest scores for those 18 questions demonstrated a slight increase in rape myth rejection scores.

Interestingly, the overall mean scores of two critical rape myth questions (4 and 18) actually increased .737 and .789, respectively. Question 4 asked, "If a girl acts like a slut, eventually she is going to get into trouble." Using a 5-point Likert-type scale with 1 (*strongly agree*) to 5 (*strongly disagree*), the pretest score was 2.737 ($SD = 1.28$), whereas the posttest score was 3.474 ($SD = 1.43$). Question 18 asked, "A lot of times, girls who say they were raped agreed to have sex and then regret it." Using the same 5-point Likert-type scale, the pretest score was 3.211 ($SD = 0.86$) compared to 4.000 ($SD = 0.88$) in posttesting. Both Questions 4 and 18 had increased scores close to 1 point, which showed an increase in rejecting rape myths. Drinking and appearance are extremely common rape myth stereotypes that need to be debunked. Hence, the trend toward increased scores of almost 1 point in the direction of rejecting rape myths is encouraging and demonstrates that the educational training using the brochure, *Sexual Assault*

Reporting: Guide for First Responders, was associated with an increased rape myth rejection for these two key items.

There were four questions (5, 15, 16, and 21) with mean scores in posttesting that showed slight decreases (i.e., more in the direction of rape myth acceptance). Question 5 asked, “When girls get raped, it’s often because the way they said ‘no’ was unclear” (4.368 at pretest; 4.316 at posttest); Question 15 asked, “A rape probably doesn’t happen if a girl doesn’t have any bruises or marks” (4.842 at pretest; 4.737 at posttest); Question 16 asked, “If the accused ‘rapist’ doesn’t have a weapon, you really can’t call it rape” (4.947 at pretest; 4.895 at posttest); and Question 21 asked, “A lot of times, girls who claim they were raped have emotional problems” (3.684 at pretest; 3.632 at posttest). These decreases in scores ranged from 0.052 to 0.105. The author wondered if the use of double negatives in the question was confusing and created the unexpected, albeit slight, increases in rape myth acceptance responses.

The author was also interested in comparing rape myth acceptance scores of the 45 police officers to myth scores reported in the literature. The Updated Illinois Rape Myth Acceptance Scale was validated in 2011 by McMahon and Farmer with 951 college students. In comparing the 22 questions of the 45 law enforcement officers’ mean scores on pretesting with the individual item mean scores of the 951 college students, scores revealed interesting findings (see Appendix K). Law enforcement officers’ mean scores were slightly higher in rape myth rejection for 19 of the 22 questions. The three questions that they scored lower on were Questions 6, 21, and 22. However, the difference in scores was minimal (0.15, 0.14, and 0.33). The overall mean score on the Updated Rape Myth Acceptance Scale for the 45 law enforcement officers was 3.92, whereas the mean score

for the 951 college students was 3.51, with a difference of 0.41. This project data suggest that college students have a higher rate of rape myth acceptance versus the law enforcement officers in this study. These data suggest that more education needs to be conducted with this population of college students, especially because this is a high-risk population for sexual assault.

Brown and King (1998) also looked at rape myth acceptance attitudes among 50 police officers (25 male and 25 female) and compared the officers' scores to 50 college students (25 male and 25 female); there was no difference in attitudes between the two groups, $F(3.96) = 0.406$. A comparison of the mean scores of the group of 19 officers who took both the pretest and posttest to the group of 26 officers who only took the pretest indicated that there was no statistical difference in their scores. Reasons that this author hypothesized as to why the 26 officers did not take the posttest included the following: they were too busy, missed work, or did not believe it was relevant. However, because their pretest scores were not statistically different than the 19 officers who took both tests, it would appear that the group who did not complete the posttest was similar to those who completed both pretesting and posttesting. Therefore, one can assume that there were no outliers who held either high or low rape myth acceptance views in the attrition group.

The effects of age, education, and race on myth scores were investigated. The statistical analysis of age revealed a bell-shaped curve in that the younger age group (20-25; $n = 1$) had a higher rate of rape myth acceptance for both tests, mean scores of 3.14, 3.59, respectively, whereas the 36-40 age group ($n = 2$) had a higher rejection rate of rape myths for both the pretest and posttest, 4.59 and 4.71, respectively. The 51-55 age group

($n = 5$) had pretest and posttest scores of 3.53 and 3.85, respectively. These data suggest that younger officers who had less experience with sexual assault victims and officers in the 51-55 age group ($n = 5$) need more education about rape myths compared to officers in the 36-40 age group ($n = 2$). The 51-55 age group ($n = 5$) is typically closer to retirement, and it can be postulated that they may have a more established belief system and ideals. In addition, this group may have had more negative experiences in working with individuals who have reported sexual assaults.

The limitation in looking at age in this sample was the use of age groupings (e.g., 20-25, 26-30, 31-35, and so on) and not using individual ages; therefore, one could only report the average score for the different age groupings (interval data) and no ratio data. The major barrier in the analysis was the small numbers in each of the cells for age category.

In investigating the effect of education on myth scores, the one participant in the high school/GED group ($n = 1$) had the highest scores for both the pretest and posttest (i.e., a higher rejection of rape myths) compared to the associate's degree group ($n = 5$), with the lowest scores for both tests (a higher rape myth acceptance). It is possible that the one individual in the high school/GED group ($n = 1$) is more open minded, has more experience, or has read more on sexual assault. Because the number of officers in each of the project's educational groupings was low, it is difficult to determine the effect of education on rejection of rape myths in this group of law enforcement officers. The mean scores on the pretest and posttest of the one individual in the master's degree/doctorate group ($n = 1$) were 3.82 and 4.68, respectively, with a 0.86 increase in their posttest score. This difference is almost 1 point on the 5-point Likert-type scale. This increase in

score is encouraging and supports the notion that additional research is needed to further evaluate the effect of educational training on rape myth acceptance attitudes using the brochure, *Sexual Assault Reporting: Guide for First Responders*.

A study by Page (2007) also investigated the effect of an educational program on rape myths and compared rape myth acceptance attitudes of 891 police officers in the southeastern region of the United States using the Rape Myth Acceptance Scale-Revised with 10 items. Page hypothesized that law enforcement officers with a higher education would have less rape myth acceptance. The Mann-Whitney analysis revealed that officers who had a high school diploma or GED had a higher rape myth acceptance than officers with an associate's degree, bachelor's degree, or master's degree ($U = 3822, p < .05$; $U = 7056, p < .05$; and $U = 485, p = .001$), respectively.

Rape myth acceptance scores based on the race of this project's participants provided some interesting findings. The one individual who marked Other had a score of 3.44 for both the pretest and posttest. This unchanged score was in the direction of a higher rate of rape myth acceptance. One individual who marked Asian American or Pacific Islander had a pretest score of 4.59 and two officers who self-identified as Black or African American had a posttest average score of 4.73. These three individuals had higher rates of rejecting rape myths. The small numbers in each of the racial/ethnic cells make it difficult to draw any solid conclusions. Interestingly, all three of these individuals are representatives of minority populations.

In the current project, gender was not found to be a significant covariate. Brown and King (1998) reported that the female officers in their study had less rape myth acceptance, $F(3.96) = 8.899, p < .0001$, compared to the male officers. In contrast, the

views of female and male students who were also studied by Brown and King were not significantly different. A study conducted by Page (2007) that surveyed 891 police officers (716 male and 150 female) found that male police officers had a higher rape myth acceptance compared to female police officers ($U = 33506.5, p < .001$). Rich and Seffrin (2012) examined rape myth acceptance scores of 429 law enforcement officers (313 male and 116 female). An author-adapted 21-item rape myth acceptance scale was used. The findings revealed statistically significant differences between female and male officers; female officers reported lower rape myth acceptance, were more likely to attend sexual assault training educational classes, and personally knew more sexual assault victims. In the current study, a similar question was asked, "How many sexual assault victims do you know, including a friend, family member, coworker, and/or self." A combination of gender and personal knowledge of sexual assault victims was not analyzed in this project due to small numbers. However, acquaintance effect was analyzed for the 19 pre and posttest participants. The two groups of officers (no personal knowledge of a victim, none, $n = 7, p = .01$, or if they knew three to four victims, $n = 5, p = .02$) had significant findings from pre to posttesting in the direction of rape myth rejection. It may be helpful for officers who personally know sexual assault victims to serve as mentors for their fellow officers because they have a better understanding of victim behaviors reflecting rape myth attitudes.

This author also looked at rank, years in law enforcement, and work experience (including the number of sexual assault cases during the officer's law enforcement career, sexual assault training, and work shift) to determine if any of these factors influenced rape myth acceptance scores. The data revealed no statistically significant differences

based on rank, the number of sexual assault cases investigated, and work shift. Rich and Seffrin (2012) reported that officers who had the following characteristics had a higher rejection of rape myths: higher rank, multiple years of law enforcement experience, were better at interviewing sexual assault reporters, and more apt to attend an educational training involving sexual assault compared to less experienced police officers. Page (2007) also analyzed police officers' work experience in handling sexual assault investigations and rape myth acceptance attitudes. Page hypothesized that officers with more experience in working rape investigations would have a higher rejection of rape myths. Her analysis showed that police officers who conducted five or fewer rape investigations scored significantly higher as to their rape myth acceptance attitudes compared to officers who worked more than 21 rape investigations ($U = 12936, p < .001$).

In the current study, law enforcement officer whose years of employment were 16-20 years 11 months ($n = 1$) had a pretest score of 3.10; the 3-6 years 11 months group ($n = 1$) had a posttest score of 3.22. Both of these two groups exhibited a higher rate of rape myth acceptance compared to the group ($n = 3$) with 7-10 years 11 months of employment, with pretest and posttest scores of 4.46 and 4.83, respectively. Since these cells were low, it is difficult to draw any specific conclusions from the data; however, the group ($n = 3$) with 7-10 years 11 months was consistent in scoring the highest on both the pretest and posttest. The subject ($n = 1$) in group 11-15 years 11 months had scores of 3.84 and 4.68 on the pretest and posttest, respectively. This increase score of .84 was the largest increase in score from pretest to posttest, indicating a higher rejection of rape myths.

Scores related to law enforcement training varied. The findings indicated that law enforcement officers with no training ($n = 2$) scored highest on both the pretest and posttest; and the officers who had 6-10 trainings ($n = 5$) scored lowest for both tests. These results were opposite of what the researcher would have expected. Did the officers with no training read more, were they more open minded? Were the officers in the group ($n = 5$) with 6-10 trainings tainted by work or did not believe in the training? The author was left wondering about what factors lead to these counterintuitive findings.

Limitations

The author acknowledged several limitations associated with this project and its evaluative research component. First, the author was a nurse and female who developed the brochure used in this project and conducted the educational session on a very sensitive subject, such as rape, to a group of predominantly male subjects. The participating officers may have wanted to portray themselves and their organization in a more beneficial light, which may have influenced their responses. Thus, the Hawthorne effect may have unduly influenced the responses given by the officers as to their perceptions of the questions on rape myths. They may have provided a social desirability response set of answers and not wished to reveal their true feelings or beliefs. Second, only 19 subjects participated in both the pretest and posttest; therefore, it is difficult to make any statistically valid conclusions about these results even within this particular law enforcement agency. In addition, this study only involved one police department in the Southwestern United States; therefore, one cannot generalize these findings to all law enforcement agencies because of its small sample size and the lack of random sampling.

Conclusions

As a pilot study, the results of this project provided baseline knowledge about the rape myth acceptance attitudes of a small group of law enforcement officers while also investigating the effect of an educational tool and training session conducted by the researcher on rape myth acceptance using a pretest-posttest design. To better understand the rape myth acceptance attitudes of law enforcement officers, a larger sample of officers is needed, preferably officers throughout the United States. Previous research studies by Brown and King (1998), Page (2007), and Rich and Seffrin, (2012) have demonstrated that law enforcement has a high rate of rape myth acceptance, while all three studies also support the fact that male officers have a higher rate of rape myth acceptance compared to their female counterparts. However, the overall mean score of law enforcement officers in this study reflected greater rejection of rape myths than found by prior researchers. Rape myth rejection by this group of officers is an encouraging finding.

The brochure, *Sexual Assault Reporting: Guide for First Responders*, is an educational tool that was created to help dispel prevalent rape myths and will be used as a resource to help eliminate barriers to reporting sexual assault by educating law enforcement, other first responders, the district attorney's office, and our communities, one person at a time. Although the results of the posttesting did not reveal statistically significant differences in scores, the overall increase in mean posttest scores after attending the author's educational session describing the content of her brochure was encouraging.

Lessons learned by conducting this project included the following: the brochure was helpful in providing discussions about rape myths and there is a need for further educational training with first responders (e.g., law enforcement, firemen, and emergency departments) using the brochure, *Sexual Assault Reporting: Guide for First Responders*, and adapting the current training brochure for use in the community. In addition, opportunities that were identified during the implementation of this project included the following: contacts with the district attorney's office regarding providing education on rape myth acceptance and its effect on reporting sexual assault crimes and with several other law enforcement agencies, which may include teaching at a police academy. In addition, this author has made arrangements to conduct educational sessions with different community-based programs in the Greater Los Angeles Area. In an attempt to reach the professional nursing community, poster presentations are planned for meetings sponsored by the Association of California Nurse Leaders (ACNL), the International Association of Forensic Nurses (IAFN), and the End Violence Against Women (EVAW) International to name a few. In addition, it is anticipated that these data will be published in a journal as a pilot study, along with continued research.

At the beginning of this project, the author anticipated that creating a brochure would start a dialogue and increase awareness about sexual assault among first responders, namely, police officers, and that goal was accomplished. The next phase in this project is to distribute the brochures to other first responders, such as firemen, emergency medical technicians, and medical personal. This brochure educates on the myths, barriers, and facilitators of sexual assault reporting and is relevant to the work done by multidisciplinary team members who work with victims of sexual assault.

Furthermore, this educational tool addresses the needs of sexual assault victims and can be used as a guide for nurses and health care providers whose role is to educate and inform victims of sexual assault. Hopefully, this will have a domino effect by providing services to victims of sexual assault that otherwise may have been avoided (e.g., medical-legal exam, crisis counseling, victim-witness services, and prophylactic treatment to prevent sexually transmitted infections and unwanted pregnancy). By increasing the reporting rates of sexual assault victims, it is expected that criminal prosecution and conviction rates will likewise increase, which, ultimately, will result in a healthier and safer society for all communities.

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APPENDIX A

**LYNCH'S FORENSIC NURSING INTEGRATED PRACTICE MODEL
REQUEST LETTER**

From: toyettabeukes
Sent: 18 March 2014 20:31
To: Rights and Permissions (ELS)
Subject: Obtain Permission - Book request

Title:	Ms.
First name:	Toyetta
Last name:	Beukes
Please select the type of publication:	Book
Book - Title:	Forensic Nursing Science
Book - ISBN:	978-0-323-06637-2
Book - Author(s):	Lynch, Virginia A. & Barbar Duval, Janet
Book - Year:	2011
Book - Pages from:	13
Book - Pages to:	13
Book - Chapter Num:	2
Book - Chapter Title:	Concepts and Theory of Forensic Nursing Science
I would like to use (please select one of the following options):	Figure(s)
If using figures/tables or illustrations please specify the quantity:	The Integrated Practice Model with the "Triangle & Flame in the Middle" I only need 1
Are you the author of the material?:	No
If not, is the author involved with your project:	No
In what format will you use the material?:	Print
Will you be translating the material?:	No
Information about your proposed use:	other
Proposed use text:	I plan on using the material for my Doctor of Nursing Practice proposal.
Additional comments/Information:	Thank You! Toyetta Beukes

APPENDIX B**LYNCH'S FORENSIC NURSING INTEGRATED PRACTICE MODEL
PERMISSION LETTER**

Dear Ms Beukes

As per your email, we hereby grant you permission to reproduce the material mentioned below at no charge subject to the following conditions:

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Kind regards

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E: s.norton@elsevier.com

Please note I am in the office on Tuesdays, Thursdays & Fridays

APPENDIX C

SEXUAL ASSAULT REPORTING: GUIDE FOR FIRST RESPONDERS

THE BRAIN & TRAUMA

Limbic System:

- **HIPPOCAMPUS** = processes information into memories.
Encoding = Organizing sensory information.
Consolidation = Grouping information into memories and storing the information.
- **AMYGDALA** = Specializes in the processing of emotional memories and works with the hippocampus.

BOTH STRUCTURES ARE VERY SENSITIVE TO HORMONAL FLUCTUATIONS

Hormones & Chemicals:

CATECHOLAMINES: Fight or flight response
CORTISOL: Energy available
OPIOIDS: Prevent pain
OXYTOCIN: Promotes good feelings

THESE HORMONES IMPAIR MEMORY CONSOLIDATION

A brain during trauma:

Amygdala (Detects Threat) > Activates Hypothalamus > Pituitary > Adrenal Glands > Kicks in the Hormonal Flood > Can Trigger a Complete Shutdown

- **CATECHOLAMINES INCREASE:** damage to memory & impairs rational thought
- **CORTICOSTEROIDS:** FIRST INCREASES for more energy THEN DECREASES reducing energy (tired) & impairing immune functioning
- **OPIOIDS INCREASE:** causes flat affect (poker face)
- **OXYTOCIN INCREASE:** causes the need to share more emotional details of the trauma

For those reasons, victims experience many emotions such as fear, stress and anxiety making it difficult for a victim to deal with their experience of violence.

Tonic Immobility (TI)

- Autonomic (involuntary and uncontrollable) mammalian response in extremely fearful situations
- Eye closure, increased breathing, paralysis, feeling cold, feeling numb, unable to vocalize
- 37-52% of rape victims experience TI during an assault
- TI is more common in victims who have previous sexual assaults (childhood, adolescence, or adult)
- TI is also known as "scared still" or "frozen with fear"

Trauma and Memory

Memories from traumas are stored differently in the brain vs. memories from non-trauma. Events associated with trauma become TRIGGERS: Anniversaries, Colors, Smells, Sounds, Movements, Objects, and any event or situation that resembles or symbolized the trauma.

SUPPORTING LAWS

The Federal Violence Against Women Act (VAWA) created two additional federal rights for sexual assault victims: (1) The sexual assault victim has the right to a forensic medical exam at no cost to the victim, and (2) The sexual assault victim can have a forensic medical exam without obligation to participate with law enforcement or in the criminal justice proceeding. This became effective in California on January 1, 2012 with Senate Bill 534.

PENAL CODE 264.2 states all victims have a right to a rape crisis advocate and support person of their choice during the sexual assault evidentiary exam or physical exam.

FAMILY CODE 6927 AND 6928 allows minors 12-17 years of age to consent or decline a medical exam, treatment, and evidence collection for sexual assault without parental consent.

EFFECTIVE INTERVIEWING:

1. Keep an open mind and have respectful demeanor.
2. Reassure victims of their safety and tell them it was not their fault.
3. Any possible efforts should always be made to minimize potential further trauma to the victim (e.g. AVOID- repetitive questioning, exerting parental power, and standing over victim).
4. Offer a support person or Rape Counselor Advocate.
5. Be considerate of privacy issues.
6. Demonstrate active listening, without interrupting the flow of the victim's narrative.
7. Do NOT rush the interview as the victim may experience memory loss, present with varying emotions from crying, to laughing and/or having a flat affect (poker face).

Document these emotional responses as they are all normal reactions.

8. At the end of the interview, ask victim if there is anything he/she would like to add to their statement.
9. Offer a medical-legal exam to the victim ASAP and alert the SART team members.
10. Explain the process, what will happen next, and victim rights.
11. Reassure the victim and thank her/him.

TO DO LIST FOR LAW ENFORCEMENT

1. Transport all items linked to the sexual assault to the hospital in paper bags (e.g., toilet paper, clothing etc.).
2. Encourage the victim not to wash, eat or drink anything.
3. If the victim uses the restroom, collect urine in a clean container and transport to SART Center. This is critical in instances of suspected drug and/or alcohol use or if any loss of consciousness.

RAPE AND BATTERING HOTLINE CONTACTS

Center for the Pacific Asian Family (all Asian Pacific Islander languages) Community Service Programs (CSP)*	1-800-339-3940
Orange County	714-957-2737
East Los Angeles Women's Center* (ELAWC)	1-800-585-6231
Peace Over Violence*	
Los Angeles	213-626-3393
San Gabriel Valley	626-793-3385
Law Enforcement ONLY	213-252-5299
Project Sister Family Services*	
Pomona and San Bernardino areas	909-626-4357
Rape Treatment Center, Santa Monica-UCLA Medical Center*	310-319-4000
Sexual Assault Response Service*	
Antelope Valley	661-723-7273
Strength United*	
San Fernando	818-886-0453
Santa Clarita Valley	661-253-0258
YWCA Greater Los Angeles Sexual Assault Crisis Services*	
Compton, South Bay, South Los Angeles	1-877-943-5778

*Spanish speaking

OTHER:

SAN GABRIEL VALLEY MEDICAL CENTER
SART CENTER 24 HOUR HOTLINE1-877-209-3049

See our Facebook page <https://www.facebook.com/SARTCenter>

TEEN LINE

Teens Helping Teens - teenlineonline.org
1-800-852-8336 (1-800-TLC-TEEN), 310-855-4673
or text "TEEN" 839863

Victim Witness Assistance Program for Financial Assistance1-800-380-3811

San Gabriel Valley Medical Center SART CENTER
438 West Las Tunas Drive • San Gabriel, CA 91776
www.sgvmc.com
SART CENTER 24 HOUR HOTLINE 1-877-209-3049
forensicteam@yahoo.com

Toyetta Boukas, RN, MSN, NP, AFN-BC
SART Director

Sexual Assault Reporting: Guide for First Responders

"Change Your Thoughts and You Change Your World"
—Norman Vincent Peale

CROSS CRIME SCENE DO NOT

RAPE myths & facts

MYTH: Sexual assault is frequently the result of miscommunication or a mistake.

FACT: Sexual assault is a crime, never simply a mistake. It is not due to a miscommunication between two people. Sexual assault is any unwelcomed sexual contact obtained without consent through the use of force, threat of force, intimidation, or coercion.

MYTH: The victim must have "asked for it" by being reckless, seductive, and/or under the influence of drugs and/or alcohol.

FACT: No one asks to be assaulted, wounded, or humiliated. This way of thinking blames the victim for the assault instead of the perpetrator.

MYTH: Women lie about being raped or use it to get even with their boyfriends.

FACT: Women do not lie about being raped with any more frequency than men or women lie about any other crime. Survivors do not normally lie about being raped. Only 36% of sexual assaults are reported and it is considered the most under-reported crime, according to National Crime Victimization Survey.

MYTH: Acquaintance rape is a less serious event than a stranger rape.

FACT: An acquaintance rape is just as serious as a stranger rape. Victims experience the same degree of trauma.

MYTH: If the victim did not physically struggle or fight back, it is not really rape.

FACT: Rapists are not looking for a fight. Offenders use many different ways to threaten and coerce in order to rape. Many rape victims do not fight back because they are fearful and feel they need to cooperate to not be harmed further.

MYTH: Most victims of rape are sexually assaulted by strangers.

FACT: 78% of sexual assaults are committed by someone that the victim knows: a friend, partner, ex-partner, acquaintance, next door neighbor, co-worker, school mate, or spouse. Whereas, 22% of rapes are committed by strangers.

MYTH: Men rape because they are sexually excited and sexually denied.

FACT: The reasons men rape are complex. Rape is about power, control, and the ability to humiliate, degrade and cause pain.

MYTH: Men who rape have mental illness.

FACT: Very few rapists have mental illness. They are most often people whom we know and trust.

ALCOHOL & SUBSTANCES RAPE myths & facts

MYTH: If a woman did not drink excessively, she would not have been sexually assaulted.

FACT: Alcohol is a device that some perpetrators use to manipulate their victim and make them helpless. These offenders may encourage alcohol use by the victim, or they may seek out a person who is already intoxicated. *Alcohol does not cause rape.*

FACT: Research demonstrates that alcohol use is associated with 50-72% of all campus sexual assaults. Many drugs like Ecstasy, Rohypnol, Ketamine, and GHB can be used to render a victim to be helpless as well.

MALE SURVIVOR myths & facts

MYTH: Only gay men are sexually assaulted.

FACT: Gay, bisexual, and heterosexual men are all just as likely to be sexually assaulted. One's current or future sexual orientation has nothing to do with being sexually assaulted. One's sexual orientation has no more to do with being sexually assaulted than being robbed.

MYTH: Only gay men sexually assault other men.

FACT: Most offenders who sexually assault other men characterize themselves as heterosexual. This fact helps to emphasize another reality— that sexual abuse is about anger, violence, and power over another person, not desire or sexual attraction.

MYTH: Sexual abuse is less harmful for boys than for girls.

FACT: The long term effects of sexual abuse can be quite damaging for both genders. The harm mostly depends on things not determined by gender (e.g., identity of abuser, duration of assault, whether victim told anyone, and whether the victim was believed and helped).

MYTH: A man cannot be sexually assaulted by a woman.

FACT: Although the majority of offenders are male, a man can be sexually assaulted by a woman.

MYTH: Sexual arousal such as an erection or ejaculation during a sexual assault means the victim consented or "really wanted it."

FACT: These are *physiological* responses that may result from physical contact or even severe stress. Sexual offenders are aware how these responses can control and discourage reporting of the crime. These responses also confuse victims which can lead to feelings of shame and/or guilt.

FACTS about Sexual Assault

VICTIMS OF SEXUAL ASSAULT ARE:

- 3 times more likely to suffer from depression
- 6 times more likely to suffer from post-traumatic stress disorder
- 13 times more likely to abuse alcohol
- 26 times more likely to abuse drugs
- 4 times more likely to contemplate suicide

AND:

- 67% of sexual assault victims are under 18
- 34% are under 12
- 14% are under 6

OUT OF EVERY 100 RAPES

- 36 get reported to law enforcement
- 12-19 leads to an arrest
- 8 get prosecuted
- 4 lead to a felony conviction

ACCORDING TO U.S. DEPARTMENT OF JUSTICE (2013), 270,000 FEMALES, 12 YEARS AND OLDER WERE SEXUALLY ASSAULTED IN 2010.

- 9 OF EVERY 10 rape victims are females
- 1 OUT OF EVERY 6 American women has been a victim of attempted or completed rape in her lifetime (2.8% attempted/14.8% completed rape)
- 17.7 MILLION American women have been victims of an attempted or a completed rape
- 1 IN 33 American men (3%) has experienced an attempted or completed rape in their lifetime
- 1 OUT OF EVERY 10 rape victims is male
- 2.78 MILLION men in the U.S. have been victims of sexual assault or rape

BARRIERS

1. Prolonged time between the assault and forensic exam.
2. Not wanting perpetrator to go to jail.
3. Fears retaliation.
4. Feels law enforcement would be insensitive or blame her/him for assault.
5. Does not want anyone to know as ASHAMED OR EMBARRASSED.
6. Feels would NOT BE BELIEVED.
7. Feels RESPONSIBLE for sexual assault.
8. Believes law enforcement COULD NOT or WOULD NOT do anything to help.
9. Does not want to GET IN TROUBLE.
10. Distrusts law enforcement and/or in the legal system.
11. Does not think it was serious enough to be labeled a crime.
12. Wishes to handle it alone.
13. Was drinking alcohol.
14. Is FINANCIALLY DEPENDENT on the perpetrator.

CULTURAL BARRIERS

ASIAN PACIFIC ISLANDER:

Language (non-English speaking), patriarchal society, loyalty to abuser if known to them, saving face, no family support, devaluation of women, lack of information about resources and their location and transportation issues, threat of deportation and exploitation of immigration status.

HISPANIC:

Language (non-English speaking), fear of perpetrator, police and/or not being believed, breaking up family unit, threats by perpetrator, perpetrator is family member, low self-esteem and threat of deportation and exploitation of immigration status.

CROSS CRIME SCENE DO NOT

APPENDIX D

QUIZ 1

CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE IN RESEARCH

Identifying the Myths, Barriers and Facilitators for Sexual Assault Reporting

You are asked to participate in a doctoral project conducted by Toyetta Beukes from the Nursing Department at California State University, Long Beach. This project will contribute to my studies and my Doctor of Nursing Practice degree. You were selected as a possible participant in this study because of your profession as a law enforcement officer who is a first responder to rape and sexual assault victims.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this project is two-fold. To explore the views of police officers about victims of sexual assault and issues surrounding the reporting of these crimes. In addition a secondary aim of the project is to evaluate the effectiveness of a brochure and roll call session to increase awareness of factors that influence reporting of sexual assault by victims of this crime.

PROCEDURES

If you volunteer to participate in this study, you will be asked to do the following:

This research study involves two phases.

Phase One:

1. You will be given a sealed packet containing one form, titled "Quiz 1" which includes the following: Informed Consent, Demographic Information with survey questions and one empty envelope labeled "Quiz #1." You will take the sealed packet and open it in a private area, preferably your home.
2. Once you have read the consent, you will complete "Demographic Information and survey questions." Once completed, you will place "Quiz #1" inside envelope labeled "Quiz #1" and seal the envelope.
3. Reading the consent and completing Quiz #1 will take approximately 15 minutes to complete.
4. You will return the sealed envelope within 48 hours and place in a selected locked and secured bin at the Pasadena Police Department. All are to return their quiz, whether you decide to participate or not, in the designated sealed envelope so not to feel separated or left out.
5. I will return throughout the week to collect the envelopes containing "Quiz #1."

Phase Two:

6. I will return within one week to conduct the educational training which will consist of having you silently read the brochure. I will then conduct the educational training by going over the contents of the brochure called “Sexual Assault Reporting: Guide for First Responders.” This will take approximately 15 minutes. An additional 5 minutes will be for questions and answers.
7. You will then be given a packet containing “Quiz #2” and an empty envelope labeled “Quiz #2”. You will be asked to take “Quiz #2” at a later time, in a private area, preferably at your home. This quiz takes approximately 15 minutes to complete.
8. You will place and seal the “Quiz #2” in the provided envelope and return it within the next 48 hours and place it in a selected locked and secured bin at the Pasadena Police Department.
9. If you decide that you do not want to participate, you can return the blank quiz as described above so not to feel separated or left out.
10. You will note that the “Informed Consent” is attached to Quiz #1 and Quiz #2 and by completing and submitting Quiz #1 and Quiz #2 this will serve as acknowledgement that you have consented to participate in the study. By leaving Quiz #1 and Quiz #2 blank, this indicates you do not wish to participate in this study.
11. Both Quiz #1 and Quiz #2 will ask you to write the first and the last numbers of your residence, the number of siblings you have, the first 2 letters of the city you were born and your favorite color. These numbers and letters will only be used to connect “Quiz #1” and “Quiz #2” scores.

POTENTIAL RISKS AND DISCOMFORTS

There are some risks involved in participating in this study. These may include the following: Breach of confidentiality, Emotional distress from questions being asked and you may feel a sense of coercion to participate. However, the researcher is taking measures to minimize these risks by doing the following: the researcher will not have any names connected with the responses to the quiz items as the “Informed Consent” signature is waived and is implied by taking both Quiz #1 and Quiz #2; both Quiz #1 and Quiz #2 will be taken in a private area; and both Quiz #1 and Quiz #2 will be locked in a secured desk, inside a locked room. To minimize emotional distress, you can choose not to answer any questions and stop taking the test at any time. In order for you to not feel compelled to participate in the study, you will take Quiz #1 and Quiz #2 out of the work environment, in a private setting. Even if you decide not to participate, you can turn in the blank quizzes inside the envelopes so to appear you have participated and so not to feel singled out.

POTENTIAL BENEFITS TO SUBJECTS AND/OR TO SOCIETY

There are no direct benefits from participating in this study. You may be gratified from knowing that you may be helping to determine the effectiveness of using this educational brochure.

Creating this brochure developed for this study will address informational needs of the first responders, such as police officers, who deal with victims of rape. This educational resource is being developed to increase awareness of myths, barriers and facilitators related to reporting sexual assault and to identify evidenced based strategies that will promote therapeutic interviewing of sexual assault victims. In doing so, it is hoped the reporting rates of sexual assault victims will increase as well as the criminal prosecution and conviction rates and ultimately, a healthier and safer community for residents.

PAYMENT FOR PARTICIPATION

You will not be financially compensated for your participation.

CONFIDENTIALITY

Any information that is obtained in connection with this study and that can be identified with you will remain confidential and will be disclosed only with your permission or as required by law. Please do not put your name or any other identifying information on the demographic information, quizzes or the return envelopes. Results will be publicly reported as group averages only. It has been agreed that Toyetta L. Beukes will share with Pasadena Police Department the data analysis of the de-identified data for their knowledge. The data will be stored in a secured/password protected file. In the event of a publication or presentation resulting from the study, no personally identifiable information will be shared including law enforcement agency.

PARTICIPATION AND WITHDRAWAL

You can choose whether to be in this study or not. If you volunteer to be in this study, you may withdraw at any time without consequences of any kind. Participation or non-participation will not affect your employment status or any other personal consideration or right you usually expect. You may also refuse to answer any questions you don't want to answer and still remain in the study. Refusal to take part in or withdrawing from this study will involve no penalty or loss of benefits you would receive otherwise. The investigator may withdraw you from this research if circumstances arise which in the opinion of the researcher warrant doing so.

IDENTIFICATION OF INVESTIGATORS

If you have any questions or concerns about the research, please feel free to contact Toyetta Beukes at (xxx) xxx-xxxx (xxx@csu.fullerton.edu) or Margaret Brady, Ph.D, RN, CPNP at (562) 985-8248 (Margaret.Brady@csulb.edu) with questions or concerns about this study.

RIGHTS OF RESEARCH SUBJECTS

You may withdraw your consent at any time and discontinue participation without penalty. You are not waiving any legal claims, rights or remedies because of your participation in this research study. If you have questions regarding your rights as a research subject, contact the Office of University Research, CSU Long Beach, 1250 Bellflower Blvd., Long Beach, CA 90840; Telephone: (562) 985-5314.

I understand the procedures and conditions of my participation described above. My questions have been answered to my satisfaction, and I agree to participate in this study. I have been given a copy of this form. By completing the attached survey, I have provided my informed consent.

Please Continue to Next Page if you decide to participate with Quiz #1. Thank you!

What are the first and last numbers of your home residence? _____

How many siblings do you have? _____

What are the first two letters of the town you were born in? _____

What is your favorite color? _____

1. Age in years

- a. 20-25
- b. 26-30
- c. 31-35
- d. 36-40
- e. 41-45
- f. 46-50
- g. 51-55
- h. 56-60
- i. 61-65
- j. 66-70
- k. 70+

2. Gender

- a. Male
- b. Female

3. Please choose one term that best describes you.
- a. White (non-Hispanic)
 - b. Latino or Hispanic
 - c. Asian American/Pacific Islander
 - d. Filipino American
 - e. Black or African American
 - f. Other Please Specify: _____
4. Please choose the number of years working as a law enforcement officer:
- a. 6 months - 2 years 11 months
 - b. 3 - 6 years 11 months
 - c. 7 - 10 years 11 months
 - d. 11 - 15 years 11 months
 - e. 16 - 20 years 11 months
 - f. 21 + years
5. Please choose your current rank/professional title
- a. Law Enforcement Officer, Training Officer
 - b. Detective, Corporal
 - c. Sergeant, Lieutenant, Captain, Commanding Officer, Chief
6. Number of Sexual Assault Cases you wrote a report about or investigated during your law enforcement career.
- a. 0 - 5 cases
 - b. 6 - 10 cases
 - c. 11 or 20 cases
 - d. 21 or more cases
7. How many sexual assault training sessions have you attended in the past as a law enforcement officer?
- a. No training
 - b. 1 - 5 trainings
 - c. 6 - 10 trainings
 - d. 11 - 15 trainings
 - e. 16 or more

8. Education

- a. High School/GED
- b. Some College (no degree)
- c. Associates Degree
- d. Bachelor's Degree
- e. Master's Degree/Doctorate

9. How many sexual assault victims do you know including a friend, family member, coworker and/or self?

- a. None
- b. 1 - 2
- c. 3 - 4
- d. 5 - 6
- e. 7 or more.

10. What is your current start work shift?

- a. 07:30 am shift
- b. 12:00 pm, 01:30 pm and/or 02:30 pm shift
- c. 07:30 pm shift

Please continue to next page. Thank you!

	Strongly agree		Strongly disagree		
	1	2	3	4	5
1. If a girl is raped while she is drunk, she is at least somewhat responsible for letting things get out of hand.					
2. When girls go to parties wearing slutty clothes, they are asking for trouble.					
3. If a girl goes to a room alone with a guy at a party, it is her own fault if she is raped.					
4. If a girl acts like a slut, eventually she is going to get into trouble.					
5. When girls get raped, it's often because the way they said "no" was unclear.					
6. If a girl initiates kissing or hooking up, she should not be surprised if a guy assumes she wants to have sex.					
7. When guys rape, it is usually because of their strong desire for sex.					
8. Guys don't usually intend to force sex on a girl, but sometimes they get too sexually carried away.					
9. Rape happens when a guy's sex drive goes out of control.					
10. If a guy is drunk, he might rape someone unintentionally.					
11. It shouldn't be considered rape if a guy is drunk and didn't realize what he was doing.					
12. If both people are drunk, it can't be rape.					
13. If a girl doesn't physically resist sex—even if protesting verbally—it can't be considered rape.					
14. If a girl doesn't physically fight back, you can't really say it was rape.					
15. A rape probably doesn't happen if a girl doesn't have any bruises or marks.					
16. If the accused "rapist" doesn't have a weapon, you really can't call it rape.					
17. If a girl doesn't say "no" she can't claim rape.					
18. A lot of times, girls who say they were raped agreed to have sex and then regret it.					
19. Rape accusations are often used as a way of getting back at guys.					
20. A lot of times, girls who say they were raped often led the guy on and then had regrets.					
21. A lot of times, girls who claim they were raped have emotional problems.					
22. Girls who are caught cheating on their boyfriends sometimes claim it was rape.					

(Payne, Lonsway, & Fitzgerald, 1999; McMahon & Farmer, 2011)

APPENDIX E

QUIZ 2

CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE IN RESEARCH

Identifying the Myths, Barriers and Facilitators for Sexual Assault Reporting

You are asked to participate in a doctoral project conducted by Toyetta Beukes from the Nursing Department at California State University, Long Beach. This project will contribute to my studies and my Doctor of Nursing Practice degree. You were selected as a possible participant in this study because of your profession as a law enforcement officer who is a first responder to rape and sexual assault victims.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this project is two-fold. To explore the views of police officers about victims of sexual assault and issues surrounding the reporting of these crimes. In addition a secondary aim of the project is to evaluate the effectiveness of a brochure and roll call session to increase awareness of factors that influence reporting of sexual assault by victims of this crime.

PROCEDURES

The first phase of this study began last week and you were asked to read the following instructions titled PHASE ONE. Please read them again.

If you volunteer to participate in this study, you will be asked to do the following:

This research study involves two phases.

Phase One:

12. You will be given a sealed packet containing one form, titled "Quiz 1" which includes the following: Informed Consent, Demographic Information with survey questions and one empty envelope labeled "Quiz #1." You will take the sealed packet and open it in a private area, preferably your home.
13. Once you have read the consent, you will complete "Demographic Information and survey questions." Once completed, you will place "Quiz #1" inside envelope labeled "Quiz #1" and seal the envelope.
14. Reading the consent and completing Quiz #1 will take approximately 15 minutes to complete.
15. You will return the sealed envelope within 48 hours and place in a selected locked and secured bin at the Pasadena Police Department. All are to return their quiz, whether you decide to participate or not, in the designated sealed envelope so not to feel separated or left out.

16. I will return throughout the week to collect the envelopes containing “Quiz #1.”

TODAY WE ARE AT PHASE TWO OF THIS STUDY

PLEASE READ THE FOLLOWING INSTRUCTIONS ABOUT TODAY SESSION WHETHER YOU WERE GIVEN INSTRUCTIONS LAST WEEK OR ARE HEARING THEM FOR THE FIRST TIME

17. Today I am conducting an educational training which will consist of having you silently read the brochure. I will then conduct the educational training by going over the contents of the brochure called “Sexual Assault Reporting: Guide for First Responders.” This will take approximately 15 minutes. An additional 5 minutes will be for questions and answers.
18. You will then be given a packet containing “Quiz #2” and an empty envelope labeled “Quiz #2”. You will be asked to take “Quiz #2” at a later time, in a private area, preferably at your home. This quiz takes approximately 15 minutes to complete.
19. You will place and seal the “Quiz #2” in the provided envelope and return it within the next 48 hours and place it in a selected locked and secured bin at the Pasadena Police Department
20. If you decide that you do not want to participate, you can return the blank quiz as described above so not to feel separated or left out.
21. You will note that the “Informed Consent” is attached to Quiz #2 and by completing and submitting Quiz #2 this will serve as acknowledgement that you have consented to participate in phase two of the study. By leaving Quiz #2 blank, this indicates you do not wish to participate in this study.
22. Quiz #2 will ask you to write the first and the last numbers of your home residence, the number of siblings you have, the first 2 letters of the city you were born and your favorite color. These numbers and letters will only be used to connect “Quiz #1” and “Quiz #2” scores. If you did not complete Quiz #1 you can still participate by completing Quiz #2.

POTENTIAL RISKS AND DISCOMFORTS

There are some risks involved in participating in this study. These may include the following: Breach of confidentiality, Emotional distress from questions being asked and you may feel a sense of coercion to participate. However, the researcher is taking measures to minimize these risks by doing the following: the researcher will not have any names connected with the responses to the quiz items as the “Informed Consent” signature is waived and is implied by taking Quiz #1 or Quiz #2 or both quizzes. In addition, both Quiz #1 and Quiz #2 will be taken in a private area; and both Quiz #1 and Quiz #2 will be locked in a secured desk, inside a locked room. To minimize emotional distress, you can choose not to answer any questions and stop taking the test at any time. In order for you to not feel compelled to participate in the study, you will take Quiz #1 and Quiz #2 out of the work environment, in a private setting. Even if you decide not to participate, you can turn in the blank quizzes inside the envelopes so to appear you have participated and so not to feel singled out.

POTENTIAL BENEFITS TO SUBJECTS AND/OR TO SOCIETY

There are no direct benefits from participating in this study. You may be gratified from knowing that you may be helping to determine the effectiveness of using this educational brochure. Creating this brochure developed for this study will address informational needs of the first responders, such as police officers, who deal with victims of rape. This educational resource is being developed to increase awareness of myths, barriers and facilitators related to reporting sexual assault and to identify evidenced based strategies that will promote therapeutic interviewing of sexual assault victims. In doing so, it is hoped the reporting rates of sexual assault victims will increase as well as the criminal prosecution and conviction rates and ultimately, a healthier and safer community for residents.

PAYMENT FOR PARTICIPATION

You will not be financially compensated for your participation.

CONFIDENTIALITY

Any information that is obtained in connection with this study and that can be identified with you will remain confidential and will be disclosed only with your permission or as required by law. Please do not put your name or any other identifying information on the demographic information, quizzes or the return envelopes. Results will be publicly reported as group averages only. It has been agreed that Toyetta L. Beukes will share with Pasadena Police Department the data analysis of the de-identified data for their knowledge. The data will be stored in a secured/password protected file. In the event of a publication or presentation resulting from the study, no personally identifiable information will be shared including law enforcement agency.

PARTICIPATION AND WITHDRAWAL

You can choose whether to be in this study or not. If you volunteer to be in this study, you may withdraw at any time without consequences of any kind. Participation or non-participation will not affect your employment status or any other personal consideration or right you usually expect. You may also refuse to answer any questions you don't want to answer and still remain in the study. Refusal to take part in or withdrawing from this study will involve no penalty or loss of benefits you would receive otherwise. The investigator may withdraw you from this research if circumstances arise which in the opinion of the researcher warrant doing so.

IDENTIFICATION OF INVESTIGATORS

If you have any questions or concerns about the research, please feel free to contact Toyetta Beukes at (xxx) xxx-xxxx (xxx@csu.fullerton.edu) or Margaret Brady, Ph.D,

RN, CPNP at (562) 985-8248 (Margaret.Brady@csulb.edu) with questions or concerns about this study.

RIGHTS OF RESEARCH SUBJECTS

You may withdraw your consent at any time and discontinue participation without penalty. You are not waiving any legal claims, rights or remedies because of your participation in this research study. If you have questions regarding your rights as a research subject, contact the Office of University Research, CSU Long Beach, 1250 Bellflower Blvd., Long Beach, CA 90840; Telephone: (562) 985-5314.

I understand the procedures and conditions of my participation described above. My questions have been answered to my satisfaction, and I agree to participate in this study. I have been given a copy of this form. By completing the attached survey, I have provided my informed consent.

Please Continue to Next Page if you decide to participate with Quiz #2. Thank you!

What are the first and last numbers of your home residence? _____

How many siblings do you have? _____

What are the first two letters of the town you were born in? _____

What is your favorite color? _____

	Strongly agree		Strongly disagree		
	1	2	3	4	5
1. In some rape cases, the woman actually wanted it to happen.					
2. Even though the woman may call it rape, she probably enjoyed it.					
3. If a girl is raped while she is drunk, she is at least somewhat responsible for letting things get out of hand.					
4. When girls go to parties wearing slutty clothes, they are asking for trouble.					
5. If a girl goes to a room alone with a guy at a party, it is her own fault if she is raped.					
6. If a girl acts like a slut, eventually she is going to get into trouble.					
7. Many so-called rape victims are actually women who had sex and “Changed their minds” afterwards.					
8. When girls get raped, it’s often because the way they said “no” was unclear.					
9. If a girl initiates kissing or hooking up, she should not be surprised if a guy assumes she wants to have sex.					
10. Many rapes happen because women lead men on.					
11. It is just part of human nature for men to take sex from women who let their guard down.					
12. When guys rape, it is usually because of their strong desire for sex.					
13. Guys don’t usually intend to force sex on a girl, but sometimes they get too sexually carried away.					
14. A rapist is more likely to be Black or Hispanic than White.					
15. Rape happens when a guy’s sex drive goes out of control.					
16. If a guy is drunk, he might rape someone unintentionally.					
17. When men rape, it is because of their strong desire for sex.					
18. It shouldn’t be considered rape if a guy is drunk and didn’t realize what he was doing.					
19. If both people are drunk, it can’t be rape.					
20. Rape mainly occurs on the “bad” side of town.					

	Strongly agree		Strongly disagree		
	1	2	3	4	5
21. If a girl doesn't physically resist sex—even if protesting verbally—it can't be considered rape.					
22. If a girl doesn't physically fight back, you can't really say it was rape					
23. Women tend to exaggerate how much rape affects them.					
24. A rape probably doesn't happen if a girl doesn't have any bruises or marks.					
25. If the accused "rapist" doesn't have a weapon, you really can't call it rape.					
26. If a girl doesn't say "no" she can't claim rape.					
27. When women talk and act sexy, they are inviting rape.					
28. A lot of times, girls who say they were raped agreed to have sex and then regret it.					
29. Rape accusations are often used as a way of getting back at guys.					
30. A lot of times, girls who say they were raped often led the guy on and then had regrets.					
31. A lot of times, girls who claim they were raped have emotional problems.					
32. Girls who are caught cheating on their boyfriends sometimes claim it was rape.					
33. When a woman is raped, she usually did something careless to put herself in that situation.					

End of Session. You have now completed the survey. I would like to thank you for your participation for this research project.

Modified by Toyetta Beukes

(Payne, Lonsway, & Fitzgerald, 1999; McMahon & Farmer, 2011)

APPENDIX F

BROCHURE EVALUATION

“Sexual Assault Reporting: Guide for First Responders”

Brochure Evaluation

Expert Panel Evaluation

Your Title _____

Please rate your perception/opinion related to the following:

Question 1 –

The accuracy of the content described in the Myths & Facts section of the brochure

Poor	Fair	Good	Very Good	Excellent
1	2	3	4	5

The value of knowing the content described in the Barriers section of the brochure.

Not valuable	Limited value	Average value	Valuable	Very valuable
1	2	3	4	5

Question 2

The accuracy of the content described in the Barriers section of the brochure.

Poor	Fair	Good	Very Good	Excellent
1	2	3	4	5

The value of knowing the content described in the Barriers section of the brochure.

Not valuable	Limited value	Average value	Valuable	Very valuable
1	2	3	4	5

Question 3

The accuracy of the content described in the Facilitators section of the brochure.

Poor	Fair	Good	Very Good	Excellent
1	2	3	4	5

The value of knowing the content described in the Facilitators section of the brochure.

Not valuable	Limited value	Average value	Valuable	Very valuable
1	2	3	4	5

Question 4

The value of the resources described in the brochure.

Not valuable	Limited value	Average value	Valuable	Very valuable
1	2	3	4	5

Please rate your perception/opinion related to the following:

Layout/Design:

Poor	Fair	Good	Very Good	Excellent
1	2	3	4	5

Title

Poor	Fair	Good	Very Good	Excellent
1	2	3	4	5

Appropriate Images

Poor	Fair	Good	Very Good	Excellent
1	2	3	4	5

Attractiveness of the Design

Poor	Fair	Good	Very Good	Excellent
1	2	3	4	5

Organization

Poor	Fair	Good	Very Good	Excellent
1	2	3	4	5

Spelling

Poor	Fair	Good	Very Good	Excellent
1	2	3	4	5

Grammar

Poor	Fair	Good	Very Good	Excellent
1	2	3	4	5

Comments/Suggestions: _____

APPENDIX G**UPDATED ILLINOIS RAPE MYTH ACCEPTANCE SCALE REQUEST AND
PERMISSION CORRESPONDENCE**

Toyetta L. Beukes, RN, MSN, NP
DNP Student

09-20-14

Sarah McMahan, PhD, LSW
School of Social Work
Rutgers University
536 George Street
New Brunswick, NJ 08901
smcmahan@ssw.rutgers.edu

RE: Updated IRMA Scale

Dear Dr. McMahan,

My name is Toyetta Lynn Beukes and I am the Director of the Sexual Assault Response Team (SART) at San Gabriel Valley Medical Center in San Gabriel, California. I am currently pursuing my doctorate at the joint California State University Fullerton, Long Beach and Los Angeles Consortium.

My doctoral project involves educating law enforcement officers about rape issues by using an educational brochure that I created. The title of this project is "Identifying the Myths, Barriers and Facilitators of Sexual Assault Reporting." This educational training first entails a demographic profile of the participant, along with a pre-test and a post-test to investigate the effectiveness of the training session.

I am formally requesting your permission to utilize the Updated Illinois Rape Myth Acceptance Scale for my study for both the pre-test and post-test. The brochure developed for this study will address informational needs of the first responders, such as police officers, who deal with victims of rape. This educational resource is being developed to increase awareness of myths, barriers and facilitators related to reporting sexual assault and to identify evidenced based strategies that will promote therapeutic interviewing of sexual assault victims.

The brochure will identify the myths of sexual assault, along with the barriers to reporting, as these topics are interrelated. The brochure will also discuss the facilitators that promote disclosure and will include information about additional resources to help guide the multidisciplinary team members in their work with victims.

When victims do not report the sexual assault or receive medical services, they lack the ability to utilize resources that are available for them (e.g., crisis counseling, victim witness services, reimbursement, medical treatment, prophylactic medications to prevent sexual transmitted infections and pregnancy). The brochure is being developed because of my role as the Director of the SART Center and as a Sexual Assault Nurse Examiner whose scope of practice includes working in a multidisciplinary team, providing education for team members and serving as an advocate for victims.

Ultimately, the goal of this brochure is to increase sexual assault awareness and reporting which will increase prosecution rates therefore creating a safer society. For those reasons, your approval in allowing me to utilize the Updated Illinois Rape Myth Acceptance Scale in my study would be most beneficial to victims and our communities.

I appreciate your valuable time and consideration.

Respectfully Submitted,

Toyetta Beukes

Response

Sarah McMahan Sep 21 2014

to me

Dear Toyetta,

Thanks for your message and request. The brochure you are planning to design and the work you are doing sounds great and important! Certainly, you have permission to use the rape myth scale I worked on with Dr. Larry Farmer.

Best of luck
Sarah McMahan

Sarah McMahan, Ph.D.
Assistant Professor
Co-Director (Acting), Center on Violence Against Women & Children
School of Social Work, Rutgers University
390 George Street
New Brunswick, NJ 08901
[848.932.4393](tel:848.932.4393)

APPENDIX H

SCRIPT 1

Introduction and Explanation

Hello, my name is Toyetta Beukes. I am from the SART Center at San Gabriel Valley Medical Center. I am conducting a research project that is part of my doctoral nursing studies at CSU Fullerton, Long Beach and Los Angeles. There are two sessions related to my project. Today, session one, I am giving you a detailed packet of information about the project. It contains a document that has a consent form, short quiz with additional demographic questions, and one empty envelope labeled quiz #1. You are asked to read all of the materials at a later time and then if you agree to participate, please follow the instructions on the consent form. The consent form will also provide you with detailed information about what you will be asked to do and the sequence of steps in this project.

These are the instructions I am asking you to follow:

1. Do not open your packet now. Instead open it later in a private area and read “Informed Consent.”
2. If you wish to volunteer for this study. Once you have read the informed consent, please continue with answering the next set of questions which ask the following:
What are the first and last numbers of your home residence?
How many siblings do you have?
What are the first two letters of the town you were born in?
What is your favorite color?
These questions are only to match both scores from Quiz #1 and Quiz #2.

3. Once you answer the previous 4 questions, you are then asked to provide some demographic information and answer questions relating to sexual assault training, and your work and personal experience.
4. Once the previous questions are answered, you will then take a 22 question survey. Once completed, place it in the envelope labeled “Quiz #1” and seal envelope. If you choose not to participate, place the uncompleted quiz in the envelope labeled “Quiz #1.”

Steps 1, 2, 3 & 4 will take approximately 15 minutes to complete.

5. Everyone should return their envelopes to this room within 48 hours and place in the locked and secured bin inside this room. With everyone returning their sealed envelopes, no one will know if you are participating or not in this collection of data.

There are no repercussions if you decide not to participate. Completing Quiz #1 is voluntary. I will return throughout the week to pick up these envelopes.

Demonstration will be given as to what is in the packet.

Does anyone have any questions so far?

Second Session Information

I will return within a week to present a 15 minute educational training that discusses information in a brochure that I developed for law enforcement officers about the myths, facts, and barriers, neurobiology of brain trauma and facilitators of sexual assault reporting. There will be a 5 minute question and answer session to follow.

This educational training is part of your mandatory training activities required by Sgt.

After the Q and A session, I will be distributing a packet that has a second quiz. You will then be given instructions on this second quiz at that time. This second quiz is also to be completed in a private area preferably in the privacy of your home. Completion of this quiz is voluntary but all will be given a quiz packet following the mandatory training.

Does anyone have any questions?

I am leaving extra packets with these instructions for those officers who may not be here today for their regular scheduled shift and who may want to participate.

Thank you

The researcher will then thank all participants for their help and cooperation in this research study.

This will conclude the session.

CONCLUSION

APPENDIX I

SCRIPT 2

Introduction and General Explanation

Hello again, my name is Toyetta Beukes. I am from the SART Center at San Gabriel Valley Medical Center. As you know, I am conducting a research project that is part of my doctoral nursing studies at CSU Fullerton, Long Beach and Los Angeles. Today I am going to conduct an education session, explain the written material in a brochure that I developed about the myths, facts, barriers, neurobiology of brain trauma and facilitators of sexual assault reporting, and finish with a 5 minute Q and A session.

At the conclusion of the session, I will distribute a packet that has an informed consent and a short quiz (it is labeled Quiz #2). Quiz #2 is in a sealed packet that you will complete in a private area, preferably in the privacy of your home. This should take 15 minutes to complete. You will place Quiz #2 in the envelope labeled Quiz #2, seal it, and return it within 48 hours and place in this locked and secured bin inside this room. You have a choice to either participate or not. There are no repercussions if you decide not to complete Quiz #2 as your participation is voluntary.

I will be returning throughout the week to pick up these envelopes.

Demonstration

I have a packet available for demonstration during the instructions.

Review of Process Before the Educational Session Begins

The instructions are as follows:

1. You are asked to read to yourself, the contents of the brochure that I created called “Sexual Assault Reporting: Guide for First Responders.” Then you will listen to my educational training which consists of reviewing the contents of the brochure.
Step 1 takes approximately 15 minutes followed by another 5 minutes for questions and answers.
2. Once completed, you will be given the packet with “Quiz #2.” Open your packet later in a private area and read the informed consent and if you agree to participate, complete “Quiz #2” a 33 question survey. Once completed, place and seal “Quiz #2” in the large envelope labeled “Quiz #2.”
3. Please return this sealed envelope to this room and place in the secured and locked bin within 48 hours.

Step 2 takes approximately 15 minutes to complete.

Did everyone receive the 1st packet, with written material containing the “Informed Consent along with Quiz #1 with Demographic information?” If you have not received it or did not complete the 1st packet and wish to participate with this 2nd packet, please follow these previous instructions given today.

Does anyone have any questions?

Officers now silently read the brochure

Officers are then given the verbal presentation

Conclusion

The researcher will thank all participants for their help and cooperation in this research study.

This will conclude the session.

APPENDIX J

INDIVIDUAL ITEM SCORES

Updated Illinois Rape Myth Acceptance Scale 22 Individual Item Questions: Pre and Posttest Means and Standard Deviation Scores

Item Number		Mean	<i>SD</i>	<i>N</i>
Q1	Posttesting	4.211	0.8550	19
	Pretesting	3.947	1.1291	19
	Total	4.079	0.9968	38
Q2	Posttesting	3.895	1.3289	19
	Pretesting	3.895	1.1496	19
	Total	3.895	1.2256	38
Q3	Posttesting	4.421	0.6925	19
	Pretesting	4.158	0.9582	19
	Total	4.289	0.8353	38
Q4	Posttesting	3.474	1.4286	19
	Pretesting	2.737	1.2842	19
	Total	3.105	1.3909	38
Q5	Posttesting	4.316	1.0569	19
	Pretesting	4.368	1.0116	19
	Total	4.342	1.0208	38
Q6	Posttesting	3.263	1.5579	19
	Pretesting	3.053	1.6150	19
	Total	3.158	1.5687	38
Q7	Posttesting	3.895	1.2865	19
	Pretesting	3.579	1.5747	19
	Total	3.737	1.4272	38
Q8	Posttesting	3.895	1.1970	19
	Pretesting	3.105	1.1496	19
	Total	3.500	1.2247	38
Q9	Posttesting	4.316	1.0569	19
	Pretesting	3.895	1.1002	19
	Total	4.105	1.0853	38
Q10	Posttesting	4.158	0.8983	19
	Pretesting	4.105	0.9941	19
	Total	4.132	0.9349	38
Q11	Posttesting	4.684	0.5824	19
	Pretesting	4.684	0.4776	19
	Total	4.684	0.5253	38

Item Number		Mean	<i>SD</i>	<i>N</i>
Q12	Posttesting	4.368	0.7609	19
	Pretesting	4.053	1.1773	19
	Total	4.211	0.9907	38
Q13	Posttesting	4.526	0.9643	19
	Pretesting	4.421	0.9016	19
	Total	4.474	0.9223	38
Q14	Posttesting	4.842	0.3746	19
	Pretesting	4.526	0.8412	19
	Total	4.684	0.6619	38
Q15	Posttesting	4.737	0.4524	19
	Pretesting	4.842	0.3746	19
	Total	4.789	0.4132	38
Q16	Posttesting	4.895	0.3153	19
	Pretesting	4.947	0.2294	19
	Total	4.921	0.2733	38
Q17	Posttesting	4.526	1.0203	19
	Pretesting	4.368	0.9551	19
	Total	4.447	0.9781	38
Q18	Posttesting	4.000	0.8819	19
	Pretesting	3.211	0.8550	19
	Total	3.605	0.9455	38
Q19	Posttesting	4.000	0.8819	19
	Pretesting	3.632	0.8951	19
	Total	3.816	0.8961	38
Q20	Posttesting	4.158	0.9582	19
	Pretesting	3.526	0.9048	19
	Total	3.842	0.9733	38
Q21	Posttesting	3.632	1.6059	19
	Pretesting	3.684	1.0029	19
	Total	3.658	1.3209	38
Q22	Posttesting	3.474	0.9643	19
	Pretesting	2.947	0.9703	19
	Total	3.211	0.9907	38

APPENDIX K

COMPARISON OF LAW ENFORCEMENT OFFICERS' MEAN SCORES WITH COLLEGE POPULATION

Comparison of Law Enforcement Officers' ($N = 45$) Mean Scores With McMahon and Farmer's (2011) College Population ($N = 951$)

	group	LE			CP		
		Mean	<i>SD</i>	<i>N</i>	Mean	<i>SD</i>	<i>N</i>
Q1	pretesting	4.07	0.99	45	3.29	1.21	951
Q2	pretesting	3.91	0.97	45	3.08	1.15	951
Q3	pretesting	4.36	0.86	45	3.73	1.09	951
Q4	pretesting	2.98	1.20	45	2.63	1.03	951
Q5	pretesting	4.40	0.94	45	4.03	1.00	951
Q6	pretesting	3.16	1.36	45	3.31	1.18	951
Q7	pretesting	3.56	1.41	45	3.07	1.20	951
Q8	pretesting	3.27	1.18	45	3.07	1.03	951
Q9	pretesting	3.98	1.10	45	3.32	1.10	951
Q10	pretesting	3.96	1.09	45	3.18	1.12	951
Q11	pretesting	4.65	0.74	45	4.15	0.84	951
Q12	pretesting	4.11	1.11	45	3.85	1.06	951
Q13	pretesting	4.47	0.84	45	3.97	1.08	951
Q14	pretesting	4.62	0.78	45	4.17	0.97	951
Q15	pretesting	4.87	0.40	45	4.30	0.88	951
Q16	pretesting	4.91	0.36	45	4.62	0.73	951
Q17	pretesting	4.38	1.05	45	3.11	1.21	951
Q18	pretesting	3.20	0.87	45	3.11	0.99	951
Q19	pretesting	3.42	0.84	45	3.17	0.99	951
Q20	pretesting	3.58	.087	45	3.27	0.94	951
Q21	pretesting	3.51	1.04	45	3.65	0.97	951
Q22	pretesting	2.80	0.94	45	3.13	0.94	951

Note. LE = law enforcement. CP = college population.